

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

PROGRESS REPORT FLAGSHIP PROJECT SUMMER

SPOKE 4 – DIGITAL INNOVATION TOWARD SUSTAINABLE MOUNTAIN

DELIVERABLE D3.0.3

Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

1. EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

The main objective of the SUMMER project is to accompany energy and water management into the digital era, showing how smart technology can boost the integrated management of water and energy systems. Digital technologies, combined with the power of 'big data' and AI-based analytics, drive unprecedented innovation in how energy and water utilities and companies manage these vital resources. To make the north-western Italy productive ecosystem ready to face this challenge, the project is developed around four research modules (RMs): (i) Monitoring and forecasting water resources and energy productivity at the watershed scale; (ii) Integrated management of energy production and use; (iii) Risk-resilient Energy and Water Infrastructures; (iv) Smart Energy and Water Distribution Systems.

1.1 OBJECTIVES

The long-term ambition of this flagship project is to accompany energy and water management into the digital era, showing how smart technology can boost the integrated management of water and energy systems. The project will generate collaborations between the research system, the production system and local institutions by enhancing research results, facilitating technology transfer and accelerating the digital transformation of businesses and production processes working towards an economic and environmental sustainability and social impact of the territories involved. In particular, the main objectives of the project can be summarized as follows:

Objective	RMs involved	Activities
To enhance ecosystem efficiency promoting an effective resource and energy management by monitoring and forecasting hydro-meteorological variables and assessing relevant environmental conditioning factors providing a dynamic water balance on various timescales, from some days to several months.	RM1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Installation and implementation of sensors for monitoring hydro-meteorological variables at Cannona, Bussoleno and Nivolet sites. • Field monitoring activities at high altitude for the quantification of snow water equivalent-SWE, both in a fixed site, and with a mobile TDR system. • Installation of an innovative sensor for the continuous quantification of flow rates in a small basin in the Olen Valley in the Monterosa2000 ski domain (Alagna, VC). • Installation and implementation of sensors for monitoring hydro-meteorological variables, SWE, and optical properties of snow at the high-elevation Istituto Mosso LTER site (2901 m asl, Alagna Valsesia).

<p>To promote the big-data revolution of monitoring and forecasting using innovative sensors, remote-sensing platforms, data-transmission tools, as well as data-storage and data-management protocols.</p>	<p>RM1</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitoring of the environmental conditioning factors and snowpack properties (e.g., density, dissolved organic carbon-DOC content, and Saharan dust) at the high-elevation, Istituto Mosso LTER site (2901 m asl, Alagna Valsesia). Implementation of data transmission systems ensuring continuous monitoring and automatic data transmission of two meteorological and nivological stations in the Gran Paradiso National Park at 2600 m asl and at the Istituto Mosso LTER site at 2901 m asl. Some antennas have been tested before finding the effective solution, now in operation.
<p>To foster the potential of digitalization toward the efficient integration of variable renewables in the power system, by enabling grids to better match energy demand and production with renewable energy community's schema, thus accelerating the decarbonization of the electricity sector</p>	<p>RM2 RM4</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conclusion of the first draft of a co-simulation platform for the integrated management of energy and water resources conceived for design/planning, automated system optimization and decision support tool.
<p>To enhance infrastructures resilience by allowing fine-scale real-time monitoring of the existing risks, drought included, as well as by providing rapid and accurate assessment of asset condition and support decision-making and adaptation.</p>	<p>RM3</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Definition of a procedure for estimating the fragility curves of high-voltage pylons from avalanche impacts. Investigations for the assessment of the impact of snow avalanches on the electricity lines in Piemonte and Valle d'Aosta regions. Calibration of a fiber-optic system for earth embankment monitoring. Geophysical investigations for the characterization of water basins in the Aosta Valley.
<p>To develop 50-year global warming risk scenario maps and statistical analysis of climate and landslides/debris/avalanches data</p>	<p>RM3</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Acquisition of climate data to study the role of climate change in relation to debris flows in Aosta Valley. Feasibility study for the implementation of a machine

to support planning and management of infrastructures.

To develop and implement innovative smart-grid solutions through smart metering and digital connectivity tools, accompanied by digital models of the networks that enable proper management of the big data generated by the sensors.

RM4
RM2

learning approach for generating landslide susceptibility maps.

- Development of a hydropower production estimation model over the entire Orco basin hydrographic network.
 - Digitalization of the new aqueduct infrastructure in the Orco valley.
 - Development of a water resource optimization model for the Orco valley basin
-

1.2 WORK CARRIED OUT PER RM IN THE REPORTING PERIOD

1.2.1 Research Module 1

Research Module n.1	Start month: 1				End month: 36			
Title: Monitoring and forecasting water resources and energy productivity at the watershed scale								
Location in Mezzogiorno: Y								
RM Leader	UNITO				Prof. Stefano Ferraris			
Partners involved	POLITO	UNITO	LINKS	UNIBAS				
Type of action:	Industrial Research							
Effort in person/months:	1.86	1.26	2.5	3.2				
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):								
<p>Enhancing ecosystem efficiency and promoting valuable resources and energy management by monitoring and forecasting of hydro-meteorological variables (precipitation, evapotranspiration, wind speed, solar radiation, discharge, snow cover and snow water equivalent, carbon budget, etc.) as well as the assessment of relevant environmental conditioning factors (soil physical properties, soil moisture, soil infiltration capacity, soil permeability, rock and permafrost stability, glacier mass balance, dust and organic compounds deposition - DOC, etc.). This is even more crucial with the electricity sector becoming more decentralized with the proliferation of small and distributed energy producers connected directly to the distribution grid. Other sectors, like for example the agricultural, water supply, skiing and risk insurance industries, likewise strongly depend on innovative digital monitoring and forecasting systems. The challenge posed by these systems is especially harsh in mountain environments, typically characterized by low connectivity and accessibility conditions.</p>								
Summary of the activities envisaged for the period detailing the contribution by each Partner/Research Team for each objective (provide measurable indicators, if available):								
Objective 1 – Innovative sensors								
Task 1 – Georadar								
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experiments of georadar devices to support the mass balance of Rutor Glacier, were carried out in collaboration with ARPA VdA, during May 22-24, 2023. <p>In particular, ground-transported and drone-mounted georadar devices were used; the surveys carried out with 500 MHz and 900 MHz antennas were aimed at investigating on the north slope of the glacier the thickness of the snowpack, up to the most superficial layers of the firn/ice of the glacial apparatus. Finally, it should be noted that the experimental acquisition and processing activities made it possible to codify a standard</p>								

georadar survey protocol and related data calibration for characterization activities with non-invasive methods of snow cover.

- Characterization and monitoring using non-invasive methodologies for the definition of digital databases of glacial and periglacial environments:
 - Ground Penetrating Radar survey (GPR) for bathymetric studies and characterization of periglacial lake sediments -at Lake Superiore at Rutor.
 - Acquisition of GPR data for estimating snowpack thickness, aimed at defining the SWE (Snow Water Equivalent) of the Rutor glacier snowpack, in collaboration with ARPA - Aosta Valley.
 - Acquisition of GPR data for the characterization of the median moraine of the Rutor glacier, in collaboration with ARPA, Aosta Valley (subject of a detailed report with ARPA).
 - Experimentation of an integrated methodology of experimental data (GPR) and modeling phase to define the ice thickness of the Indren glacier (scientific article illustrating the methodology and results obtained, submitted to an international journal, under review).

GPR survey for periglacial environments

A ground penetrating radar (GPR) survey was carried out at the lake Superiore del Rutor (Aosta Valley); the survey was performed with a radio-controlled vessel, towing a GPR antenna operating at the main frequency of 200 MHz and the radar central unit. The main goal was to characterize the bathymetry of the lake and to study the bottom sediments. The lake was formed in the last 50 years, following the retreat of the front of the part of the Rutor glacier facing the La Thuile valley, at an altitude of approximately 2600 m a.s.l.

The main scientific interest is to estimate the volume of water of the basin and to estimate the sediments and sedimentation process within the basin, that could be related to the erosion and solid transport process due to the retreat of the glacier.

Figure 1 - overview from North-East of the lake Superiore at Rutor with glacier's front in background.

The survey was conducted with an IDS K2 ground penetrating radar system equipped with an IDS antenna at the central frequency of 200 MHz, installed on board the radio-controlled vessel.

Figure 2 - lake Superiore at Rutor, in foreground the radio-controlled boat

Figure 3 - detail of the vessel and the GPR system

Figure 4 - example of radargram for the bathymetric survey; on the right the depth scale for the conversion from traveltimes to depth (m).

Figure 5 - thickness of the water column, lake Superiore at Rutor, as resulting from the interpretation of radargrams

The main results obtained are summarised as:

- characterization of the sediments in the delta area of the tributary to Lake Superior, caused by the solid transport resulting from the melting phase of the glacier;
- mapping of the lake's bathymetry, with digital data available with a mesh of 10 m x 10 m (CSV format).

Snow Water Equivalent – Rutor glacier

The georadar survey was carried out in the months of May-June 2024, in collaboration with ARPA Val d'Aosta, aiming at estimating the Snow Water Equivalent (SWE) on a part of the Northern slope of the Rutor glacier.

The data acquisition of ground penetrating radar measurements was performed with a 900 MHz antenna along a series of profiles, as shown in figure 6, for a total length of approximately 4500 m.

Figure 6 - disposal of the GPR transect over the glacier surface to detect the SWE on the Northern slope of the Rutor glacier.

The ground penetrating radar measurements were calibrated at different points using probe measurements for the accurate estimate of the seasonal snow thickness. The calibration allowed us to estimate an average velocity value of propagation of the radar waves in the snow (about 0.22 m/ns), in order to convert the radargrams into depth sections. An example of a ground penetrating radar section (radargram) is shown in figure 7.

Figure 7 - example of radargram to estimate the SWE at the Rutor glacier; the red line detect the boundary between the seasonal snow and the firn-ice

The georadar profiles were collected starting from the summit area of the glacier (about 3300 m a.s.l.) up to the level of the Northern front of the glacier itself. The thickness of the seasonal snow varied between approximately 3 m and a maximum of approximately 6-7 m.

The average density values were found to be approximately 350-400 kg/m³.

The statistical analysis of the data and the integration of the information acquired from the georadar data with the measurements from the probes are carried out by ARPA VdA; the overall interpretation is reported in the ARPA technical reports, aimed to define the mass balances of the glacier (not included in this report).

Partner/Research teams: POLITO

Task 2 – Time domain electromagnetic for the characterisation of aquifers –

Test site of Bussoleno

- Integrated methodologies of electrical and electromagnetic tomography for the characterization of aquifers in a valley bottom environment:
 - Experimentation of the TDEM electromagnetic device (ABEM WalkTEM) for the stratigraphic characterization of soils, aimed at determining the hydrogeological parameters of the subsoil, to depths exceeding 200 m.
 - Development of algorithms and codes in Python environment for the interpretation of time domain electromagnetic soundings (TDEM); algorithms were developed for processing porosity and water saturation data, starting from electromagnetic data (always TDEM) and from electrical tomography data.

- Experimentation of integrated methodologies of electromagnetic type (TDEM) and electrical resistivity tomography for the characterization of a test site (Susa Valley) of hydrological and hydrogeological interest (activity in collaboration with Prof. Ferraris' group).

An integrated Time Domain electromagnetic (TDEM) and electrical tomography (ERT) was performed to support the characterization of surface aquifer: the activities focused on the on the test site of Rio delle Boine Catchment of Bussoleno (Val di Susa – TO), according to the arrangement shown in figure 8.

Figure 8 - plan view of the test site with disposal of the TDEM soundings and with the transect of electrical tomography (ERT) (red line, with coordinate 0 m located at Ovest).

The measurements were carried out with a Syscal R1 device – IRIS Instrument (France) – 72 channels for electrical tomography investigations and with a TDEM WalkTem2 device for the electromagnetic survey in the time domain, with a transmitting loop of 40 m x 40 m.

The electrical resistivity tomography was carried out with 72 electrodes, 3 m spacing among electrodes, with a Wenner-Schlumberger configuration array (1287 quadrupoles), and a dipole-dipole forward (1290 quadrupoles) and dipole-dipole reverse (1100 quadrupoles), with a current cycle of 250 ms.

The data processing consisted in the reconstruction of the apparent resistivity pseudosection and the inversion with ResIPy code in a Python environment.

Results of the ERT

The maximum investigation depth of the resistivity sections is a function of the electrode configuration, the overall length of the electrode array and the resistivity distribution of the subsoil; in this specific case, a resistivity section was obtained up to approximately 35-40 m from ground level.

The following main structures are highlighted:

- the top layer is characterized by electrical resistivity values in the range of (200-400 ohm m), with the presence of conductive structures in the initial and central part of the section; this response is compatible with the presence of medium-sized materials, in an abundant fine matrix; low anomalies resistivity (blue areas in the interpretative section) can be associated with possible preferential pathway of infiltration and surface recharge from of the aquifer;
- at depths between a few meters and approximately 20-25 m, high resistivity structures are highlighted, associated with the presence of coarse-sized materials, with few amount of fine matrix;
- at greater depths, the resistivity values of 500 – 600 ohm m can be associated with the presence of an aquifer (to be verified with any information regarding the electrical conductivity of the groundwater).

Figure 9 - vertical section of electrical resistivity (values in ohm m) from the inversion of the Wenner-Schlumberger data; (no topography correction) – Section West to East

TDEM survey

The electromagnetic survey was carried out with WalkTme2 TDEM device (ABEM Instrument) were using a transmitting loop of 40 m x 40 m, a receiving coil of 10 m x 10 m, with dual moment and high moment mode acquisition for each sounding, a time window of 10 ms, and 40 samples distributed over the time window.

The data processing involved an initial stacking of the measurements, the analysis of the response curve with respect to time and the subsequent conversion into the resistivity domain; finally, we performed the inversion with the Occam model (1D), to elaborate the vertical profile of the electrical resistivity with respect to the depth.

The interpretation of the sounding n.1 is herein reported; the low quality of the data of soundings n.2 and n.3 does not allow the quantitative processing.

In figure 10, the observed response curve (left) and the 1D electrical resistivity model of the S1 survey are shown (plot on the right).

Figure 10 - sounding S1; left) curve of the low moment response (red) and high moment (green); right) 1D-model of electrical resistivity.

The superficial layers are characterized by high electrical resistivity values, with values above 100 ohm m; these values can be associated with the presence of coarse material with reduced presence of water.

A first electrically more conductive horizon (with resistivity in the range 30-60 ohm m, potentially hosting the groundwater, is identified at a depth between 20 m and 30 m. A second conductive formation (values around 10 ohm m) is detected at the depth between 50 m and 80 m. The resistivity values can be associated with fine (clayey) formations, but the presence of aquifer horizons cannot be excluded.

Partner/Research teams: POLITO

Task 3- AUTOSALT in the Olen Catchment (Alagna Valsesia, VC).

We have now one complete year of data in the Olen Catchment (another AUTOSALT has been installed at the Rio delle Boine catchment (Bussoleno, TO), but the SD card has been tampered and probably no data are available t the moment. It is starting now to work properly.

Figure 11 - Flow measurement instrument AUTOSALT with continuous saline solutions at the Alagna Valsesia (VC) site operating since September 2023 (a second instrument was installed in summer 2024 in Bussoleno).

The stage-discharge relation in the Olen Catchment has been calibrated along the year and it is depicted in Fig.12.

Figure 12 - Stage-discharge curve at the Olen Catchment obtained with AUTOSALT

The resulting time series of discharge is shown in Fig.13. The huge amount of snow in April interrupted the acquisition until the beginning of May. The great storage of water in the catchment and the precipitation in the summer caused high discharges in summer.

Figure 13 - Level and discharge time series at the Olen Catchment obtained with AUTOSALT.

Partner/Research teams: POLITO

Objective 2 – Monitoring

Task 1 – Water Balance

The four main sites (Bussoleno, Nivolet, Mosso, Garstelet) have increased the number of instruments and the data are in the repository.

Data Report DIST is the metafile explaining the contents of the hourly data CSV files with the results of:

- Monitoring in the Rio delle Boine FOREST Catchment (Bussoleno, TO).
- Monitoring in the Nivolet GRASSLAND Catchment (Valsavarenche, AO).
- Monitoring of discharge with AUTOSALT dilution in Olen Catchment (Alagna, VC)
- Monitoring of soil moisture with Cosmic ray in Orba Catchment (Carpeneto, AL)

Data Report DISAFA-DST is the metafile explaining the content of CSV files regarding:
Monitoring in the glacialized Garstelet Catchment (Gressoney, AO).

Figure 14 – Nivolet weather station

Figure 15 - The reflectance of the surface measured with the ROX instrument at the Nivolet station (2550 m asl).

Figure 16 – Snow melting, water balance description.

Figure 17 - The ROX instrument measuring the multispectral reflectance of the surface at the Mosso station (2900 m asl).

Figure 18 - The Garstelet station (3500 m asl).

The DIST group has installed 4 new soil moisture and temperature profiles with Centro Funzionale Aosta at Ollomont, Valsavarenche, Gressoney and Ayas, with the objective of obtaining a network of 12 sites in Valle d'Aosta (from different institutions such as CFVDA,

POLITO, ARPAVDA and CVA) of soil moisture and temperature measurements at the end of the year.

Regarding the low cost Arduino sensor for substituting the STS sensor in the measurement of water level, water electrical conductivity and temperature has been finalized by Labflux-DIST and installed in some streams of forest Rio delle Boine catchment (Bussoleno, TO) and 16 units will be installed both in the forest site, and in the grassland high altitude catchment. A picture of it is shown in Fig.17.

Labflux logger: External connections

Labflux logger: Internal layout

Figure 19 - External and internal views of the low cost Arduino sensor for water level, water electrical conductivity and temperature measurement in streams and springs.

Partner/Research teams: UNITO, POLITO

Task 2 – Snow Water Equivalent

The ANAVS data using GNSS has had some problems at the Nivolet station due to the weak GSM field, which can be solved in the next weeks.

In Fig.18 some ANAVS data show interesting dynamics, compared with snow depth, but probably there is a bias to be corrected and more data have to be processed during the month of October.

Figure 20 - Comparison of doppler snow depth with SWE from ANAVS and CRNS at the Nivolet station (2550 m asl).

The use of innovative sensors for continuously measuring SWE at high elevation (LTER Istituto Mosso pilot site), through the measurement of cosmic rays neutron sensing (CRNS, Finapp) and based on the signals of the global navigation satellite system (GNSS, ANavS), has been extensively tested. The results have been compared to manually obtained SWE, to hourly/daily HS measurements at the automatic weather station (AWS) installed at the site, and to hourly/daily simulations performed with the SNOWPACK® model, thanks to a collaboration with the Comando Truppe Alpine – Servizio Meteomont (hereafter: Meteomont). The CRNS probe estimated well the evolution of the snowpack during the winter and spring, as can be deduced from the comparison between probe data and ad-hoc manual measurements performed by UNITO (Fig. 18). However, the comparison with SNOWPACK® model and manual measurements performed by Meteomont did not provide high-quality results (Fig. 19), likely due to the following reasons: (i) underestimation of simulated SWE by SNOWPACK® due to inaccurate input data acquired by the local AWS; (ii) manual measurements performed by Meteomont personnel that did not consider the entire snowpack (only the most surficial snow layers were analyzed) and carried out far from the CRNS measuring site; (iii) preferential accumulation of snow at the CRNS site due to wind effect. The CRNS probe stopped functioning at the end of April due to the infiltration of water into the IP68 box which, however, did not cause irreparable damages (details below). In addition, the performance of the GNSS system has also been tested, providing poor results.

Indeed, a slight snow creep occurred at the snowpack on the slope behind the station. The two GNSS antennas differentially moved due to the snow creep, causing high errors in the measurements, preventing the use of the data. To avoid snow creep issues at the Mosso Station, the mast system has been moved farther away from the slope (approx. 5 meters); this will allow us to acquire more accurate SWE data during the snow season 2024/2025. Furthermore, the use of newly designed IP68 boxes will allow us to prevent water infiltration in the CRNS systems, ensuring continuous measuring periods.

Figure 21 - Comparison between CRNS (Finapp) data and manual measurements performed by UNITO.

Figure 22 - Comparison between CRNS probe with: manual measurements performed by UNITO and Meteomont, as well as data simulated using SNOWPACK© model.

In addition to the relocation of the mast system at the Mosso Station, a new weather station, also equipped with a GNSS system, has been installed in the Monte Rosa massif area, close to the Garstelet Glacier (3500 m asl). The station measures the following parameters with a 10 minutes time resolution: air temperature, relative humidity, atmospheric pressure, wind

velocity and direction, precipitation (intensity, cumulative, type and weight), visibility, snow height, SWE, liquid water content of the snowpack, and snow layer temperature (every 50 cm ranging from the ground level to 200 cm above ground).

Regarding the investigation of the optical properties of snow and the influence of organic compounds (DOC) on the snow melting rates, an autonomous field spectrometer (JB RoX) has been used at the Mosso site. The data acquired by the instrument (Fig. 21) are currently under investigation and will be subject to an extensive post-processing to correct the biases caused by the unevenness of the snow surface both at the daily and sub-daily scale. Moreover, snow samples have been collected during the winter and spring, to be analyzed for DOC and nitrogen content. Saharan dust has also been collected and will be analyzed in the next weeks/months.

Figure 23 - Raw data obtained by the JB RoX.

During the summer, water samples have been collected from the ponds located close to the Istituto Mosso, and will be analyzed for DOC and nitrogen content. In addition, CTD probes have been installed in the ponds, to be also used as a surrogate measure of SWE during the winter time, taking advantage of the changes in water pressure under the ice cover. Moreover, experimental, low-cost snow-depth stakes have been installed at the site, in collaboration with the Glaciological Service of Lombardy.

Finally, a time-lapse camera has been installed at the Mosso site, to analyze the fractional snow cover. However, some issues occurred to the transmission system, thus the camera is currently not operational; operations to fix the issues are planned for the next weeks.

Partner/Research teams: UNITO

Objective 3 – Data Analysis and Forecasting

Task 1 – Machine Learning for River Discharge

Development of machine learning tools which will be useful in the data analyses and forecasting activities of the next six-months period. The DAUIN Polito team is developing a system to forecast river discharges using open data rainfall data provided by UniTO.

Partner/Research teams: UNITO, POLITO

Task 2 – Deep Learning for aboveground biomass and Snow Water Equivalent estimation

Development of deep learning tools to further enhance downstream forecasts regarding river discharges using aerial and Remote Sensing data. LINKS team is working on a system able to estimate the expected aboveground biomass from aerial images, as well as exploring the feasibility of providing reasonable estimates of Snow Water Equivalent (SWE) from InSAR and other remote sensing sources. In the last six months, activities have focused on extending the biomass estimation framework. The model for Canopy Height Model estimation of the study area is being integrated with a framework capable of tree detection and subsequently tree crown delineation. The area of the tree crown, together with the canopy height, will help to provide a precise estimate of the biomass in the area of interest. The tree detection task is performed through the open source Python library DeepForest, which includes a pre-trained RetinaNet model trained on images from the National Ecological Observatory Network (NEON) with a semi-supervised approach. This model can be directly applied to make predictions for new data or adopted as a robust and automated label generator for retraining purposes.

The model produces bounding boxes that identify the tree. Each bounding box annotation is returned with its x min , y min , x max , y max coordinates, and predicted probability score (the probability that the bounding box represents a tree) ranging from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating greater confidence in the prediction. To reduce overcounting among overlapping tiles, DeepForest sorts predictions by confidence scores and removes lower scoring overlapping boxes (i.e. non-maxima suppression). Figure 22 displays the RGB input that is given to the model and the corresponding output in the form of bounding boxes.

Figure 24 - The RGB input of the model and the corresponding output (bounding boxes).

The bounding boxes can be exploited as prompts for SAM (Segment Anywhere Model), an open-source foundation model released by Meta AI Research for promptable segmentation. In fact, SAM can segment any object in an image by using various input prompts, such as points, bounding boxes, or freeform masks. It's designed to work with minimal user input, automatically detecting and segmenting objects even in unfamiliar or complex images. In this case, the EfficientSAM version was used: it is designed to improve the efficiency and speed of segmentation tasks. While SAM is highly versatile and powerful, EfficientSAM focuses on reducing the computational cost, memory usage, and inference time, making it more suitable for real-time or resource-constrained environments.

We applied this technique at scale on aerial images acquired over South-West Piedmont, to produce a set of binary GeoTIFF images. These images can be then polygonised transforming them into more manageable vector shapes, and subsequently merged with the CHM to assign a single height value to each tree crown, based on the shape's raster content. This process is ongoing and will be refined in the next months. Future work will focus on merging these multiple outputs into a single biomass estimate.

Figure 25 shows the input for the model (RGB image + prompt) and the output represented by the segmentation mask of the tree crown inside the input bounding box.

Figure 25 - . An example of RGB input + prompt (left) and the output (tree crown delineation, right)

Figure 26 - An inference for tree crown delineation using SAM at large scale.

Considering Snow Water Equivalent (SWE) estimation from EO data, a literature review of existing works has been carried out, allowing for the selection of baseline frameworks and data sources to adopt for the preliminary studies that will be carried out in the next months, focusing on the North-West Alps for validation purposes.

Partner/Research teams: LINKS, UNITO, POLITO

Task 3 – Hydrological Modelling

Activities focused on the use of the DREAM hydrological model to reproduce single flood events at daily scale. This task is essential to ensuring the reliability of the distributed initial soil moisture conditions by D-DREAM, which will be then utilized as input for the implementation of DREAM model at hourly scale (H-DREAM). For this purpose, the most significant rainfall events selected in previous months were considered. DREAM simulations were evaluated comparing simulated versus measured time series and flow duration curves, both relative to the entire record of observations. This semester's activity focused on the analysis and modeling of hydrological variables in Fiumarella of Corleto basin at different spatial and temporal scales. In a first step, soil moisture data collected by TDR probe (hourly continuous measurement since 2006) were filtered and analysed for each flood event. Efforts were made to fill gaps in soil water content using 1 km GSSM satellite data. This combination enabled a clearer delineation of pre-event conditions and improved estimates of soil sorption capacity. Simultaneously, the lag time between precipitation and runoff was evaluated by comparing theoretical formulas and observed data to identify the optimal lag time. Hydrological modeling was carried out with both D-DREAM and H-DREAM by using the Hortonian and Dunnian models for surface runoff production. Special emphasis was placed on the Hortonian mechanism, which showed a better fit in capturing the immediate basin response to precipitation events by highlighting the impact of permeability on basin

response. In addition, regarding the sub-catchment, input maps for hourly-scale modeling were finalized and some flood events were selected for successive modeling analysis.

Partner/Research teams: UNIBAS

Task 4 – Machine learning for mountain recharge of aquifers

Deep learning models were trained and compared for the weekly forecast of the water table depth measured by the three regional sites in Vottignasco, Savigliano and Racconigi. The implemented models use as input exclusively meteorological data in the form of a time series of rasters (a video) of cumulative precipitation, maximum temperature and minimum temperature up to two years prior to the week to be forecast. Two different deep learning models were implemented, one already consolidated in the literature based on convolutional networks (CNN) and recurrent networks (LSTM), called here TDC-LSTM, and another, proposed in this work, called UnPWaveNet developed starting from WaveNet architecture proposed by Google DeepMind in 2016. The two models produced satisfactory results but focused on different aspects of prediction. The UnPWaveNet model was able to better model the dynamic behavior of the groundwater time series, obtaining better results in terms of KGE (Ferraris et al., IDRA2024)

Partner/Research teams: UNIBAS

Outputs since the start of the RM:

17 publication have been published so far.

Journal Paper (see Table 8 for more detail)

1. Bearzot, F., et al. "[Hydrological, thermal and chemical influence of an intact rock glacier discharge on mountain stream water.](#)" *Science of The Total Environment* 876 (2023): 162777.
2. Painter, Kevin J., Alessio Gentile, and Stefano Ferraris. "[A stochastic cellular automaton model to describe the evolution of the snow-covered area across a high-elevation mountain catchment.](#)" *Science of the Total Environment* 857 (2023): 159195.
3. Gentile, Alessio, et al. "[Towards a conceptualization of the hydrological processes behind changes of young water fraction with elevation: a focus on mountainous alpine catchments.](#)" *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 27.12 (2023): 2301-2323.
4. Nicola Colombo et al. "[Unprecedented snow-drought conditions in the Italian Alps during the early 2020s.](#)" *Environmental Research Letters*, 18 074014.
5. Gentile, Alessio, et al. "[Technical Note: two-component Electrical Conductivity-based hydrograph separation employing an EXPonential mixing model \(EXPECT\) provides](#)

[reliable high temporal resolution young water fraction estimates in three small Swiss catchments](#)". *EGUsphere [preprint]*;

6. Baiamonte, Giorgio, et al. "[Applying different methods to model dry and wet spells at daily scale in a large range of rainfall regimes across Europe](#)." *Advances in Statistical Climatology, Meteorology and Oceanography* 10.1 (2024): 51-67.
7. Colombo, Nicola, et. al. "[High-resolution temporal variations of nitrate in a high-elevation pond in alpine tundra \(NW Italian Alps\)](#)". *Catena*, 107635.
8. Colombo, Nicola, et al. "[Editorial: Hydrological and chemical effects of a changing cryosphere on mountain freshwaters](#)". *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 11.
9. Salerno, Franco, et al. "[Cooling and drying induced by Himalayan glaciers under global warming](#)". *Nature Geoscience*;
10. Gisolo, Davide, et al. "[Evapotranspiration of an abandoned grassland in the Italian Alps: Modeling the impact of shrub encroachment](#)", *Journal of Hydrology*, 635.
11. Brighenti, Stefano, Colombo, Nicola, et al. "[Factors controlling the water quality of rock glacier springs in European and American mountain ranges](#)". *Science of the Total Environment*, 953.
12. Liyew, C., Ferraris S., et al. "[Analysis of diurnal air temperature trends and pattern similarities in Highland and Lowland stations of Italy and UK](#)", in *International J. of Climatology*, Royal Soc. Of Met.
13. Scandellari F., Ferraris S. et al. "[Using stable isotopes to inform water resource management in forested and agricultural ecosystems](#)", in *J. Environmental Management*, 365
14. Liyew, C., Ferraris S., et al. "[Identifying Time Patterns of Highland and Lowland Air Temperature Trends in Italy and UK across monthly and annual scales](#)", accepted by *Advances in Statistical Climatology, Meteorology and Oceanography*

Publication in conference proceeding (see Table 8 for more detail)

15. Galatola, Marco, et al. "[Land Cover Segmentation with Sparse Annotations from Sentinel-2 Imagery](#)." *IGARSS 2023-2023 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*. IEEE, 2023
16. Arnaudo E. et al. "[FMARS: Annotating Remote Sensing Images for Disaster Management using Foundation Models](#)". IEEE, 2024
17. Monaco S., Monaco L., Apiletti D. "[Uncertainty-aware segmentation for rainfall prediction post processing](#)". ACM, 2024

Deliverables (see Table 4 for more detail)

- **D3: Geodatabase Structure.** Definition of the Geodatabase structure for the Digital Twin Implementation.

- **D4: First Progress Report.** First year progress report of the flagship project.
- **D5: First Dataset Delivery.** First delivery of an integrated dataset containing data from the 4 RMs.
- **D6: Digital Twin (Beta Version).** A Beta version of the Digital Twin platform containing results and datasets of the 4 RMs.
- **D7: Innovative Sensors (First Release).** A first release of a document describing an innovative procedure for monitoring and quantifying the water supply in small basins that are poorly monitored by regional functional centres, providing information such as real-time flow and current SWE at altitude.
- **D8: Second Progress Report.** Second year progress report of the flagship project.
- **D9: Second Dataset Delivery.** Second delivery of an integrated dataset containing data from the 4 RMs.

Participation to international conferences

- EUCOP 2023
- ISSW 2023
- EGU 2024
- IEEE 2024
- ACM 2024
- EMS 2024

Datasets

- [Integrated Dataset of the Four Research Module.](#)
- [Water Balance – Innovative Sensor Example](#)

IPR

- Research activities led to the filing of a patent related to the development of an innovative methodology for monitoring small mountain basins. The patent application was accepted without reservation on 25 Oct 2024.

Results:

Objective1-Task1:

A radio-controlled vessel, towing a GPR antenna has taken measurement at the lake Superiore of Rutor to estimate the volume of water of the basin and to estimate the sediments and sedimentation process.

Objective1-Task2:

The new Time Domain electromagnetic apparatus has taken measurements in two dates for the characterisation of aquifers of Rio delle Boine catchment (Bussoleno, TO). They have been integrated with electrical tomography (ERT) obtaining that between a few meters and approximately 20-25 m high resistivity structures are highlighted, associated, with the presence of coarse-sized materials.

Objective1-Task3:

The automatic salt dilution apparatus has completed a whole year test at the Olen catchment with satisfactory results. A stage discharge curve has been obtained also with some high stage measurements in the beginning of summer. A second apparatus has been installed at Bussoleno site but the SD card was tempered: its measurements will start in November.

Objective2-Task1:

A very detailed set of hourly measurements is now in the repository. The DISAFA group has integrated the data with the meteorological data of Centro Funzionale Aosta, while the DIST group has installed 4 new soil moisture and temperature profiles with Centro Funzionale Aosta with the objective of obtaining a network of 12 sites in Valle d'Aosta (from different institutions) of soil moisture and temperature measurements at the end of the year. The Garstelet site at 3500 m asl has been installed and a new Arduino sensor for stream and spring measurements is ready for application.

Objective2-Task2:

The cosmic ray CRNS and the ANAVS GNSS have been compared with manual measurements at Mosso with a bias to be investigated. The comparison of CRNS with snow depth at Nivolet, and new comparison with ANAVS will start next months. New, continuous meteorological, SWE, and hyperspectral data series acquired in high mountain areas of Nivolet and Mosso sites.

Objective3-Task2:

The first activities involved curating a large-scale dataset utilizing worldwide open sources such as the National Ecological Observatory Network (NEON), which includes high-resolution RGB aerial data comparable to our study areas Piedmont and Valle d'Aosta valleys in Italy.

Figure 27 - Dataset sample, comprising a Very-High-Resolution RGB image (left), and the corresponding Canopy Height Model (CHM).

Deep learning has been used for biomass estimation with aerial images acquired over South-West Piedmont, and validation will be carried out in the next months, focusing on the North-West Alps.

Objective3-Task3:

At daily scale, hydrological modeling showed satisfactory results in the representation of the different flow regimes, with NSE (Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency) and KGE (Kling-Gupta Efficiency) values being in the range of 0.67 to 0.82. Moreover, it was found that the distributed configurations on average outperformed the lumped configuration in terms of accuracy, offering a more detailed description of the spatial variability in the basin. The adoption of multi-objective calibration schemes, based on both base flow and water balance, further enhanced the physical significance of the results.

Figure 28 - Comparison between the simulated and recorded daily streamflow for the "Fiumarella of Corleto" basin (a) and flow duration curves (b) of the period 2004-2011.

At hourly scale, the use of a model based on Hortonian infiltration mechanism proved effective in capturing the immediate response of the basin to precipitation events, realistically simulating the triggering of surface runoff. At this regard, good consistency was found between hourly simulated flow rates and those observed directly in the field, confirming the model's ability to accurately represent flow dynamics on small time scales.

Table 1 - Flood events considered for the analysis.

Progr	Events	Duration [h]	Total Rainfall [mm]	Event Lag-Time [h]	Satellite Soil Moisture	TDR Soil Moisture	Observed Peak flow [m ³ /s]	Simulated Peak flow H $\alpha=0.1$ [m ³ /s]	err [%]
G_31	01/12/2013	64	125	-	NaN	0,374	41,77	38,38	8,12
G_14	18/02/2011	55	21	4,42	0,317	0,242	29,07	26,28	9,60
G_20	04/02/2019	15	23,65	3,16	NaN	0,05	24	17,62	26,58
G_21	17/03/2016	39	48,19	2,64	NaN	0,266	22,97	23,34	1,61
G_1	24/01/2003	49	68,33	3,34	0,307	NaN	22,69	20,34	10,36
G_17	07/03/2017	32	46,26	3,97	NaN	0,188	20	21,13	5,65
G_7	22/01/2009	15	20,51	4,08	0,304	NaN	19,54	17,66	9,62
G_10	10/03/2010	23	36,42	5,89	0,317	NaN	17,99	14,11	21,57
G_19	08/05/2018	5	23,62	2,5	NaN	0,272	15,66	28,15	79,76

Figure 29 - Examples of comparison between the simulated and recorded hourly flood events.

Objective3-Task4:

Deep learning has been used for weekly forecast of water table depth in South-West Piedmont, using the meteorological data of ARPA Piedmont taken in the Grana and Maira headwater mountain catchment.

Deviations (if applicable):

N/A

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

All the equipment has been bought. In the last semester May to October 2024, new high performance batteries and solar panels have been bought for the site without electrical

supply at Nivolet at 2550 m asl. Also, helicopter and horses have been employed to transport heavy materials.

Consumables for the evapotranspiration calibration have been also bought.

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

- Testing of all sensors in the cold (and snowy, if any) season in all sites. Now all sensors have been installed.
- Testing of the distributed measurement of snow water equivalent with the portable Network Analyzer.
- Testing of the ANAVS GNSS sensor (SWE) also at the Nivolet site in the winter and spring seasons (it has been already tested at the Mosso site, with a much better GSM field).
- Testing of the internet connection in the site without electrical supply and low GSM field at Nivolet at 2550 m asl.
- The mentioned patent proposal submitted in October 2024 at the Patent commission of Università di Torino will follow the next steps for the patenting procedure.
- To write and test machine learning scripts using the data collected from the sensors in the Bussoleno (forest) and Nivolet (grassland) catchments water balance.

1.2.2 Research Module 2

Research Module n.2	Start month: 1				End month: 36			
Title: Integrated management of energy production and use								
Location in Mezzogiorno: N								
RM Leader	POLITO				Prof. Alfonso Capozzoli			
Partners involved	POLITO	UNITO	LINKS	UNIVDA				
Type of action:	Industrial Research							
Effort in person/months:	4.06	0.32	2.20	0.10				
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):								
<p>The primary objective of the Research Module 2 is the conceptualization, development, and deployment of a co-simulation architecture to deeply study and analyze the integrated management of energy and water resources within renewable energy communities located in mountain areas. The proposed architecture was designed to easily operate models from various software platforms, each characterized by different temporal resolutions. The goal is to create an effective and robust tool for generating digital twins of renewable energy communities. This tool was conceived to support both the design stage of renewable energy communities and the optimization during operation of energy and water management, along with the integration of data analytics services to support the decisions of various stakeholders.</p> <p>Two main goals have been achieved during the reporting period:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) Enhancing the co-simulation architecture's capabilities to model the thermal behavior and dynamics of buildings within an energy community. ii) Efficiently integrating large-scale water reservoir models specifically designed for a case study aligning with the primary objectives of the NODES project. 								
Summary of the activities envisaged for the period detailing the contribution by each Partner/Research Team for each objective (provide measurable indicators, if available):								
Objective 1: Enhancement of the co-simulation architecture for integrated management of energy and water resources in Renewable Energy Communities.								
<i>Task 1 – Design of the co-simulation architecture</i>								
<p>The co-simulation architecture has been carefully designed and refined to accommodate new energy models, described in the following sections. Several adjustments have been made to ensure compatibility between the different simulation components, focusing on data exchange mechanisms, synchronization, and scalability. These modifications involved integrating energy models with the co-simulation platform, ensuring that each model could effectively communicate and interact with the others. The adjustments also enhanced the coordination of</p>								

the models across different simulation environments, providing a robust framework for simulating complex energy systems, including generation, distribution, and end-use.

Figure 30 - Urban energy modeling generic workflow

Moreover, the co-simulation architecture has been extended with flexible and modular tools addressing data management issues and enabling the definition of a City Information Model (CIM) for complex Urban Energy System (UES), as described in Figure 30.

The proposed tool aims to create a standardized CIM for the chosen case study area, regardless of the quality of input provided by users (e.g., researchers, administrators, etc.). The solution not only converts inputs into a standard CIM format but also retrieves missing data through automatic downloads, theoretical assumptions, and statistical estimations. Once the CIM model for the selected territory is obtained, it can be automatically integrated into the co-simulation environment to run simulations and analysis.

Figure 31 Architecture Overview

The proposed solution implements several modules to provide the flexibility required for modeling UES. It offers a predefined workflow that, based on the input provided, can be initiated

at any stage, allowing for both automatic and user-defined characterization of the final information model. The solution integrates heterogeneous data inputs and generates a complete CIM, even in cases of limited data availability.

The approach has been designed to operate independently from data availability. To achieve this, a bottom-up methodology is combined with statistical assignments and theoretical assumptions to fill in missing information (e.g., building heights, envelope types), ensuring the highest possible consistency with real-world conditions.

The architecture, as shown in Figure 30 is organized into two main layers:

i) **Data Source Layer**

ii) **Model Extraction Layer**

The tool provides a specific workflow that progresses from raw data inputs to a complete output, such as a CIM in CityJSON. However, the framework's modularity allows interaction with intermediary steps of the workflow, enabling the pipeline to be initiated at any point. If detailed information is already available, the corresponding data-filling modules can be bypassed, while the remaining modules can be executed. This flexibility allows the entire process to be run in a single continuous sequence or by utilizing each block individually, with inputs provided at any stage without needing to ensure completeness. This modular execution also facilitates the inspection of intermediary outputs. The rest of this section describes each layer of the proposed solution.

Data Source Layer

In the Data Source Layer, thanks to configuration parameters, it is possible to set up the starting condition of both raw inputs and setup for the desired final CIM output.

Referring to Figure 31 we can observe the diverse nature of the data handled by the proposed solution. Besides the semantic difference of these data, it is also important to notice that some of these can be uploaded as raw inputs (e.g. *Utility Network Data*, *Shapefile Data*), others are automatically retrieved by external web data sources (e.g. *OSM Data*), some of them are strictly related to the specific case study (e.g. *DTM/DSM*) others can be used for multiple case studies having a Regional or National validity (e.g. *Census Section Data* and *TABULA archetypes*). Each of these data sources is explained in the following bullet points:

- *OSM Data* are geo-referenced polygonal information, retrievable from Open Street Map (OSM), representing the buildings in a defined study area. They usually come with attached information that can be used during the workflow.
- *ShapeFile Data* are provided by the user and contain geo-referenced information for

building descriptions.

- *DTM/DSM Data* indeed represent the Digital Terrain Model (DTM) and the Digital Surface Model (DSM), which are georeferenced models containing the elevation of the ground above sea level and the elevation of surface elements above the ground. These files can be automatically retrieved and are useful for the building's height estimation.
- *Census Section Data* provides urban-level statistics at high spatial resolution. This is a powerful source of information, providing census section-level information on population, families, buildings, economics, and social records.
- *TABULA Archetypes* builds national typologies according to sharing features (envelope layering, common HVAC systems, etc.). The proposed solution relies on those archetypes for classifying buildings, characterising each with energy-related information (e.g. Transmittance values, envelope thermal resistance, etc.).
- *Weather Data* can be provided or gathered through Meteostat API, allowing data retrieval according to the specified resolution and time interval.
- *Utility Network Data* can be uploaded, supporting the PandaPower data format. This format consists of a series of data frames describing all the network objects from lines to transformers; with this kind of file, any LV-MV power grid can be represented.

Data consistency and configurability are two of this solution's main focus involving particular input data. For all the data that are not automatically retrieved by this solution, a major problem is to ensure the same nomenclature and structure. Thus, dedicated modules and configuration files allow us to explicitly provide a meta description of raw inputs, enabling the tool to assess them correctly. In conclusion, the flexibility and the configurability of the platform allow for different inputs to be integrated in the future.

Model Extraction - Data Preparation

As shown in Figure 31, the **Data Preparation** includes all the modules performed at the beginning of the workflow.

The first module, *Bounding Box Generation* in Figure 31, delimits the study area around a specified address. The bounding box can be either a square area centered in the address location or a circular area; in the first case, the desired distance fixes the length of the square side, while in the second one, the circle's radius.

The *OSM Data Loading* module executes some operations involving a connection to the OSM Application Programming Interface (API) to get raw data referred to the desired study area inside the bounding box. Using the package OSMnx requested data are downloaded and then arranged in a GeoDataFrame with a predefined structure.

ShapeFile Loading module crops the input ShapeFile data (if provided) within the previously generated bounding box and stores geometries and associated tabular information into a GeoDataFrame.

Consistency Checking module ensures consistency among the two datasets (the one from OSM and the one from the user input) for later joining. Most joining procedures are based on spatial knowledge. Thus, the control performed by this block focuses on indexing, Coordinate Reference System (CRS), and geometries. In addition to that, based on configuration files, it ensures the correct nomenclature for each type of data in the two GeoDataFrames.

Lastly, the *Census Section Data Loading* module allows users to upload tabular census data. These can provide demographic and economic statistics related to each census zone; they must be georeferenced, but they could differ from country to country. To maintain consistency, a configuration file allows for the specification and linking of the nomenclature for the specific features needed in the characterisation.

To summarise, OSM building data, ShapeFile building data, and census section data are now available as GeoDataFrames. These preliminary outputs of Data Preparation will be fed to the core process of this workflow: *Data Processing*.

Model Extraction - Data Processing

The Data Processing step, labeled as step 2 in the workflow (Figure 31), includes all the modules that perform geometric operations and fill in missing information. The output is a complete dataset containing the required building information and city-wide characterization, ready to be converted into a standardized CIM in CityJSON.

First, the Geometric Operations module integrates various data sources into a single dataset. This step reconstructs a complete georeferenced data frame with all the buildings in the study area and performs essential geometric calculations, such as gross and net floor area. The combination of shapefiles and OSM data allows for checking missing geometries, while each building is assigned the census section code to which it belongs.

Next, the Data Filling module addresses the absence of specific information for each building in the case study area:

- i. Height
- ii. Year of construction
- iii. Number of floors
- iv. Use destination
- v. Infiltration rate
- vi. Desired Demographic information

This module parses the geodataframe from the previous module, and when some data is missing, it calls the specific helper method to fill it. This process is automated and mostly configurable, especially for the fixed theoretical assumptions (e.g. average infiltration rates). Data filling operation replicability is ensured. This module can be configured to specify statistical data sources and corresponding nomenclature, assuming these new data sources will provide the same information.

The data-filling process utilizes different methodologies depending on the type of data being addressed. For example, geometric calculations are used to estimate building heights, a statistical approach is applied for determining the use classification, and theoretical assumptions are employed to assign general values, such as the average floor height specific to the case study area. When information regarding the year of construction is missing, the average construction year for the census zone in which the building is located is assigned.

Building height can be estimated through two approaches. The first approach uses average height values per census zone, if available. The second approach involves utilizing DTM (Digital Terrain Model) and DSM (Digital Surface Model) data, which are downloaded via the OE API. In this approach, the height is determined by the difference between DSM and DTM values, and these height points are spatially joined and averaged for each building. The accuracy of these methods is highly dependent on the resolution of the data sources, affecting the reliability of the results. The pipeline's modularity allows for the integration of more advanced height estimation procedures.

The number of floors is calculated by dividing the total building height by the assumed average floor height.

Building use classification is typically provided in the OSM data; in its absence, default values can be configured to fill in the missing information.

The infiltration rate, representing the default air exchange rate of a building, can be manually set by the user.

Demographic data is statistically derived for each building by analyzing distributions within the corresponding census zones. Key variables include the number of families and family types residing in each building. Additional demographic data can be specified and included in the final output if necessary.

The Outliers Filtering module enables data cleaning by performing two primary operations: i) removing entries with erroneous or extreme values (e.g., buildings that are excessively low or high); and ii) selecting buildings based on specified characteristics, such as residential or commercial use, or buildings constructed before a certain year.

The Building Archetype module assigns each building a construction archetype based on the year of construction and the number of families. This classification follows the TABULA Physics Library,

allowing the retrieval of detailed information on the building envelope, heating and cooling systems, and any retrofits performed over time..

Model Extraction - Data Transformation

The Data Transformation step involves the final conversion of data into a 3D CIM. CityJSON is a JSON-based format derived from CityGML, which uses XML. Both CityJSON and CityGML are standard data formats for describing city information models. In this case, they have been augmented with additional information on weather and utility distribution networks. JSON was chosen for its lightweight nature and faster encoding/decoding compared to XML. This step comprises four modules, as shown in Figure 31.

The Geometry Reconstruction module ensures that geometries are compliant with CityJSON. In this format, each surface is registered as part of a building object, so it is necessary to compute the exact position of each building vertex and correct surface orientations. This process creates a 3D model with a Level of Detail (LoD) of 1.2, meaning buildings are represented as extruded boxes based on their height. Once the geometries are reconstructed, the Conversion to CityJSON module generates the appropriate file and populates it with basic building objects. This file serves as the baseline for the complete CIM, with additional information from the two Application Domain Extensions (ADE) being mapped onto it.

The Energy-Related Data Mapping module applies the energy extension schema, which has been developed in accordance with the CityGML ADE specifications, to model the thermal behavior of buildings.

In addition to energy-related data at the building level, utility distribution network information is integrated at the city level, enabling simulations and the development of energy-saving strategies. The Utility Network Data Preprocessing and Mapping module enriches the model using data from PandaPower files. It maps the utility network in the study area and associates each building with the nearest point of delivery (POD), bus, or injection/extraction node..

Partner/Research teams: POLITO

Task 2 - Development and integration of a scalable process to build and deploy energy performance models in a renewable energy community.

In the reporting period several activities were carried out to improve the simulation capabilities of the co-simulation architecture.

The first activity focused on enhancing the pipeline for defining and describing building envelopes. This improvement increased the scalability of the process, enabling more detailed and complex representations of construction elements and materials in accordance with EnergyPlus

conventions. Materials and construction details are specified using JSON files, allowing for greater flexibility beyond standard archetypes and enabling users to define the most appropriate characteristics for specific case studies.

In the second activity a new approach for modelling heating systems in buildings was conceived. According to this approach the model of the building, developed in Energy Plus, is coupled with two models developed in Modelica as showed in Figure 32.

Figure 32 – Modelling approach of heating systems in buildings

The first model, known as the "ambient model," is used to represent the dynamics of terminal units interacting with the indoor environment. This model receives information from EnergyPlus about indoor air temperature and mean radiant temperature and uses this data to evaluate the radiative and convective heat exchange between the terminal unit and an air volume representing the building, while considering a specific supply temperature provided by the generation system. Three different types were defined for this model to describe the behavior of water-based radiators, fan coils, and radiant floors. Figure 33 shows the Modelica model for the radiator type.

Figure 33 – Details of Ambient Model in Modelica

This model is particularly noteworthy because it includes a thermostatic valve controlled by a PID controller, which adjusts the flow rate based on the difference between the indoor air temperature and the desired setpoint. This approach provides a more accurate representation of the thermal dynamics of heating systems within the co-simulation architecture.

The second model, referred to as the "Plant Model," is used to simulate the dynamics of generation systems coupled with a thermal energy storage unit, which acts as a buffer between demand and production. This model receives the return water temperature and water mass flow rate from the "Ambient Model." These inputs are used to calculate the heat demand from thermal energy storage. The storage unit is connected on the supply side to a heat source, which provides water at a defined temperature, emulating the high-temperature water provided by a generation system. The mass flow rate on the supply side is constant, and the on/off operation of the circulation pump can be controlled through an external interface. Figure 34 displays the Modelica model.

Figure 34 - Details of Plant Model in Modelica

The model calculates the energy supplied to the water, considering the return water from the tank on the supply side. The input energy required by a specific heat generation technology (e.g., gas-fired boiler or heat pump) is determined based on predefined efficiency curves.

These models, which involve numerous parameters, require careful initialization. Various routines have been tested to automate this process, ensuring the scalability of the proposed co-simulation architecture. The implementation of these models represents a significant advancement in the modeling and emulation capabilities of the proposed tool, enabling effective simulation of renewable energy communities.

Partner/Research teams: POLITO

Task 3 - Development and integration of a water multi-reservoir model for the co-simulation platform at daily /hourly scale

The software tool identified for the water reservoir modelling is *Generalized Multi-Reservoir Analyses using Probabilistic Streamflow Forecasts (GRAPS)*, in which reservoirs and users across the basin are defined using a node-link representation. Unlike existing reservoir modeling software, GRAPS can handle probabilistic streamflow forecasts represented as ensembles for performing multi-reservoir prognostic water allocation and evaluate the reliability of forecast-based allocation with observed streamflow.

Figure 35 - GRAPS flowchart.

As depicted in Figure 35, GRAPS offers a useful Python GUI to design the multi-reservoir model as a network of water components. The water components are highlighted in the example model legenda. The GRAPS GUI allows for the initialization of the file required by the GRAPS EXECUTABLE, the solver of the multi-reservoir model written in Fortran90. Moreover, the GRAPS GUI can execute the GRAPS EXECUTABLE and retrieve the output file for visualization purposes. As a consequence, the type of execution of GRAPS EXECUTABLE is a One Shot Execution as shown in Figure 36.

Figure 36 - Stepping of GRAPS model.

To achieve the interconnection of GRAPS EXECUTABLE with the co-simulation architecture the One Shot Execution solver was transformed into a Time Stepped Execution solver, capable of producing output from input received each time step as depicted in Figure 36. The stepping of GRAPS EXECUTABLE was achieved with a flexible GRAPS Interface designed in Python that is

capable of exploiting the co-simulation infrastructure i) to receive Inflow data as input by the co-simulation scenario, ii) set properly the input file required by GRAPS EXECUTABLE to run a single time step, iii) calculate the multi-reservoir model solution by executing the GRAPS EXECUTABLE, iv) retrieve the output file containing the multi-reservoir model solution, v) send to the co-simulation scenario the water system balance of the multi-reservoir model. Moreover, the GRAPS Interface deals with the co-simulation API to receive management commands for the data exchange, time synchronization, and regulation. A high-level description of the GRAPS Interface is depicted in *Figure 37*.

Figure 37 - GRAPS co-simulation interface.

To test the GRAPS Interface, a simple scenario was proposed where the Inflow data is read from the former inflow input file of the original GRAPS EXECUTABLE by the CSV Reader simulator. This simulator is a Python simulator capable of reading a CSV file and sending one of the values at each time step. These values are fed via the co-simulation infrastructure to the GRAPS model as shown in *Figure 38*. The water system balance as output of the GRAPS Interface instead is redirected via the co-simulation infrastructure to the HDF5 Collector, a Python simulator that can retrieve each time step water system balance state and save it into a Water System DB to store the results of the GRAPS EXECUTABLE.

Figure 38 - First water reservoir co-simulation environment.

The Braxil Example scenario contained in the repository of GRAPS have been used for validation purposes. Firstly, GRAPS EXECUTABLE has been executed in a One Shot Execution to retrieve the result of the standalone simulator. Then, the co-simulation infrastructure have been run in the configuration of *Figure 38* to retrieve the co-simulated simulator result. Finally, the result of the simple co-simulation scenarios have been compared. This experiment demonstrated the capability of the co-simulated GRAPS Interface to reproduce the same result of the standalone GRAPS EXECUTABLE.

Starting from the last semester, activities moved to Research Module 4 as explained in Deviations section.

Partner/Research Team 1: POLITO

Objective 2: Development of a case study in Orco Valley by means of the co-simulation architecture.

Task 1 - Development of the Orco Valley Reservoirs network and evaluation of the water need for hydro-potable service.

This task was aimed at the implementation of the GRAPS GUI (see *Figure 39**Figure 38*) to execute a co-simulation environment as proposed in (Objective 1 – Task 3) of the Valle Orco. This modelling process requires the following steps:

1. Thoroughly analyzing the system's structure, with a specific focus on interconnections and the hydraulic system.
2. Determining the necessary inputs, which includes:
 - a. Supply side characterization:
 - i. Establishing the physical parameters for each reservoir, such as storage limits and operational parameters.
 - ii. Estimating coefficients for the Elevation-Storage Relationship and Area-Storage Relationship for each reservoir.
 - iii. Estimating evaporation rates for each reservoir.
 - b. User-side characterization:
 - i. Examining the technical and operational characteristics of existing hydroelectric power plants.
 - ii. Profiling and characterizing a representative user with municipal water requirements, particularly related to a new aqueduct project in the area.

Figure 39 - Part of the GRAPS water reservoir model of Valle Orco.

Starting from the last semester, activities moved to Research Module 4 as explained in Deviations section.

Partner/Research Team 1: POLITO

Task 2 – Simulation of thermal behavior and energy demand of a renewable energy community: the case of Frassinetto municipality

This task was aimed at the implementation of the modelling process of energy demand of the buildings in Frassinetto Municipality to execute and test the co-simulation environment as proposed in (Objective 1 – Task 2). Eventually, the aim is to assess the performance of various Renewable Energy Community scenarios by means of grid and building-level KPIs. Frassinetto is a mountain village in the North-West of Italy. The degree days for this specific area are 3826. According to ISTAT data, the population stands at 272 persons. Utilising a GIS file of the region, whose representation is reported in *Figure 40*, 150 residential buildings were identified within Frassinetto. These buildings exhibit an average net surface area of 140 m².

Figure 40 – GIS representation of the buildings of Frassinetto.

Three archetypes of building envelope elements were developed to represent three different performance classes (low, medium and high). Using the national technical standard UNI/TR 11552:2014 [21], specific constructions consistent with the geographical location of the Frassinetto scenario were modelled within the EnergyPlus environment.

To cover the heating energy needs, the heating distribution system is assumed to have aluminium radiators for both HP and GB systems, as these water terminals also work well at relatively low water temperatures. The HP and GB systems were sized during the initialisation phase, and nominal capacities were calculated based on the specific energy performances of the buildings.

Concerning renewable generation, the DSM and the building footprints of Frassinetto were used to extract the rooftop surfaces of the buildings. All surfaces with an orientation between North-West and North-East and an inclination more significant than 60° were excluded as they have few equivalent hours and, therefore, have low annual producibility. The suitable surfaces were fully exploited, assuming that the maximum peak power is installed. The most common PV technology on the market was considered, particularly a panel c-Si type with an area of 1.63 m^2 and a peak power of 330 W. Total PV system losses are assumed to be 14%.

According to these definitions, six different building categories were identified: i) buildings with high-performing envelopes equipped with a heat pump, ii) buildings with high-performing envelopes equipped with a gas-fired boiler, iii) buildings with medium-performing envelopes equipped with a heat pump, iv) buildings with medium performing envelope equipped with a gas-fired boiler, v) buildings with low performing envelope equipped with a heat pump, and finally vi) building with low performing envelope equipped with a gas-fired boiler. For the building models, a fixed window-to-wall ratio was imposed on each surface equal to 0.2.

Eventually, a scenario is defined by selecting the number of buildings falling in one of the six categories previously introduced and the percentage of prosumers, determining the amount of electrical energy locally generated. Four different scenarios were identified and analysed in the present work.

- Scenario 0 - Baseline: This scenario depicts the existing condition within the REC. It features medium to low building envelope performance. Heat generation relies on traditional, gas-fired boilers, and the penetration of photovoltaic (PV) panels is minimal—sufficient to sustain the concept of a REC but not extensively deployed.
- Scenario 1 - PV deployment: In this scenario, the focus is on maximising the installation of PV panels to meet the electrical demands of the community. To achieve this, the number of prosumers is increased. The maximum installed PV capacity is assumed for each prosumer. In this scenario, there is no enhancement in building envelopes or heat generation technologies, emphasising the potential of solar energy within the constraints of current infrastructure.
- Scenario 2- Integrated PV and HP: This scenario explores the synergy between extensive PV panel installations and a moderate penetration of HP systems. It does not account for substantial improvements in building envelope performance compared to the baseline, highlighting the energy transition through renewable electricity and efficient heating solutions.
- Scenario 3 - Comprehensive retrofit: In this comprehensive scenario, high PV penetration and HP installations are combined with significant improvement of the building envelopes compared to the baseline. The aim is to demonstrate a holistic approach to energy efficiency, where enhanced envelope performance reduces heating demand, complemented by renewable energy generation and efficient heat pump technology.

The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) reported in *Figure 41* are evaluated hourly for each scenario, considering metrics at REC and building level.

Figure 41 – Schematics of electrical energy flows within a REC and relevant KPIs.

- **Building Self-Consumption:** it refers to the proportion of locally generated electricity consumed by the prosumer itself to cover the load, without being fed into the grid concerning the total of locally generated electricity. It measures how effectively a prosumer can use electricity generation to meet demand. Assuming a passive sign convention, the total net energy measured the overall energy withdrawn/injected from/to the grid. This metric is calculated for each building equipped with PV panels.
- **Building Self-Sufficiency:** it indicates how much a building can cover its electricity demand from its generation sources. Unlike self-consumption, self-sufficiency is evaluated as a ratio of the total energy demand and the generated energy that meets over a given period, highlighting the building's ability to rely less on external energy supplies. This metric is also evaluated for buildings equipped with PV panels, similar to self-consumption.
- **REC Energy Withdrawn from the Grid:** it represents the total electrical energy drawn from the grid by the members of the REC. For buildings classified as consumers, it is determined by the sum of electrical demand from plug loads and energy conversion systems. In the case of prosumers, it is calculated as the net electrical demand after accounting for local electricity generation.
- **REC Energy Injected to the Grid:** it represents the total electrical energy injected to the grid by members of the REC. The surplus from local electricity generation systems of the prosumers generates it.
- **REC Shared Energy:** Following the Italian standard for a REC, shared energy is calculated as the minimum, hourly, between the power injected into the grid and the energy drawn from the grid. This quantity is evaluated at the community level and represents a "virtual" quantity, as the sharing is not performed physically.
- **REC Virtual Self-Consumption:** it refers to the proportion of energy injected to the grid that effectively contributes to shared energy. It serves as a measure of the efficiency of the REC in utilising surplus generation for shared energy purposes.

Table 2 summarises the KPIs, including: i) electrical energy withdrawn from the grid by the Renewable Energy Community (REC), ii) electrical energy injected to the grid by the REC, iii) shared energy within the REC, iv) average self-sufficiency of the prosumers within the REC, v) average self-consumption of the prosumers within the REC, and vi) virtual self-consumption of the REC.

Table 2

Scenario	E_{wh}^{REC} [MWh]	E_{in}^{REC} [MWh]	SE [MWh]	SS_{avg} [%]	SC_{avg} [%]	VSC [%]
Scenario 0	22,6	6,3	3,8	48,6	19,6	59,3
Scenario 1	20,5	20,1	4,3	50,3	19,8	21,7
Scenario 2	132,2	12,3	11,9	36,3	50,3	96,8
Scenario 3	94,4	13,6	12,1	39,3	49,2	88,9

Scenario 0, serving as the baseline, reflects current conditions with minimal photovoltaic (PV) installation and a low self-consumption rate (19.6%). However, the Renewable Energy Community (REC) manages to share 59.3% of the prosumers' surplus, highlighting the positive impact of the community setting. It is worth noting that the REC's primary purpose is to provide environmental, economic, or social benefits to the members rather than to generate financial profits. Therefore, following the incentive scheme on shared energy of the Italian regulatory framework [9], the REC's business model makes the economic investment in renewables affordable, i.e., with a payback period less than the lifetime of the renewable plants with a VSC of at least 55%. As a consequence, Scenario 0 results in a techno-economic feasible energy community.

Scenario 1 considers only a higher penetration PV installation with respect to the baseline, resulting in a substantial increase in electrical energy supplied to the grid by the REC (from 6.3 MWh to 20.1 MWh). This comes alongside a significant reduction in virtual self-consumption (from 59.3% to 21.7%), indicating that, despite the community setting, members face challenges in effectively sharing energy.

Scenario 2 introduces PV panels and moderate heat pump (HP) technology penetration. This leads to an expected increase in electrical energy withdrawn (132.2 MWh) and a decrease in energy supplied to the grid (12.3 MWh) as the average self-consumption rate among prosumers rises to 50.3% (up from 19.8% in Scenario 1). This scenario demonstrates a marked shift, with a significantly higher energy rate shared within the REC (11.9 MWh) and the highest virtual self-consumption rate (96.8%). It suggests a synergic effect of integrating PV and HP technologies in enhancing the REC's energy self-reliance and efficiency.

Scenario 3 features significant improvements in building envelope technologies, leading to a reduction in electrical energy withdrawn (94.4 MWh) compared to Scenario 2 due to decreased heating energy needs. The energy supply to the grid increases to 13.6 MWh. Self-sufficiency improves to 39.3% (up from 36.3% in Scenario 2), due to the reduced heating demand related to the higher envelope performance of the building. However, virtual self-consumption (88.9%) decreases compared to Scenario 2 despite increased shared energy. This suggests that the REC in Scenario 2 was more effective in sharing the PV surplus, likely due to higher electrical demand prompted by less efficient envelope technologies than in Scenario 3.

Figure 42 presents the electrical energy balance of the Renewable Energy Community (REC) with the grid, illustrating patterns of electrical energy supplied to the grid from the prosumers' PV surplus (labelled as 'PV to Grid' in yellow solid line), electrical energy withdrawn from the grid to power the REC (labelled as 'Grid to REC' in blue solid line), and the shared energy (red area).

Figure 42 – Different energy flows with the grid in case of a) Scenario 2 and b) Scenario 3.

Partner/Research teams: POLITO

Objective 3: Application of AI algorithms for photovoltaic infrastructures mapping and potential from aerial images

Task 1 – Photovoltaic panel detection from aerial images

The tasks focused on developing a machine learning-based algorithm capable of identifying photovoltaic panel installations from aerial images. First, a dataset of PV panels composed of very-high-resolution (VHR) aerial imagery, specifically focusing on the region of Piedmont in Italy has been constructed. It comprises 105 large-scale images, providing more than 9,000 manual annotations, also including the PV panel category. A semantic segmentation machine learning model has been trained on this dataset, applying some modifications to address the specific issues of this task, such as the wide range of scales of the installations and the sparsity of the annotations. To further refine the final output, a post-processing polygonization algorithm tailored for PV panels has been developed. It processed rough raster predictions into cleaner and more precise polygons more practical to use.

Developed model allows a more efficient identification of solar plants in a given area, providing valuable data for the estimation of the amount of electrical energy produced.

Figure 43 - Example output of the solar panel detection model

Partner/Research teams: LINKS

Task 2 – Rooftop identification for photovoltaic potential assessment from aerial images

The aim of this task is the development of a machine-learning model able to identify rooftops from aerial images, to estimate their photovoltaic potential. This model has been trained using a publicly available dataset of high-resolution aerial images, with the primary goal of delimitating rooftops and distinguishing between flat and sloped roofs, for which the inclination direction is also estimated. Additionally, an algorithm has been devised to refine the model's output. Starting from the raw predictions, this algorithm aims to eliminate any inaccuracies in outlining each rooftop while also calculating the surface area and orientation angle. These latter two pieces of information are then utilized to provide an estimate of the annual photovoltaic potential that each rooftop can yield.

Figure 44 - Example output of the roof detection model

Partner/Research teams: LINKS

Outputs so far:

6 publication have been published so far.

Journal Paper (see Table 8 for more detail)

- Rando Mazzarino P., Macii A., Bottaccioli L., Patti E., [A Multi-Agent Framework for Smart Grid Simulations: Strategies for power-to-heat flexibility management in residential context](#). In: Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks, Elsevier.
- Solinas F. M., Macii A., Patti E., Bottaccioli L., [An Online Reinforcement Learning Approach for HVAC Control](#). In: Expert Systems with Applications, Elsevier.
- Arnaudo E., Blanco G., Dominici F., [A Comparative Evaluation of Deep Learning Techniques for Photovoltaic Panel Detection From Aerial Images](#). In: IEEE Access.
- Coraci D., Brandi S., Hong T., Capozzoli A., [An innovative heterogeneous transfer learning framework to enhance the scalability of deep reinforcement learning controllers in buildings with integrated energy systems](#). In: Building Simulation.
- Silvestri A. et al, [Real building implementation of a deep reinforcement learning controller to enhance energy efficiency and indoor temperature control](#). In: Applied Energy, Elsevier

Publication in conference proceeding (see Table 8 for more detail)

- Innocenti L., Blanco G., Barco L., Rossi C., [Maximum Temperature Prediction Using Remote Sensing Data Via Convolutional Neural Network](#). In *IEEE MetroLivEng, IEEE*
- Brandi S., Pizza A., Buscemi G., Razzano G., Capozzoli A., [Enhancing energy efficiency and flexibility in educational buildings through a deep reinforcement learning-based controller for rooftop units](#). In *Proceedings of the 9th International Building Physics Conference (IBPC 2024) Volume 3: Building Systems and HVAC Technologies*

Deliverables (see Table 4 for more detail)

- **D3: Geodatabase Structure.** Definition of the Geodatabase structure for the Digital Twin Implementation.
- **D4: First Progress Report.** First year progress report of the flagship project.
- **D5: First Dataset Delivery.** First delivery of an integrated dataset containing data from the 4 RMs.
- **D6: Digital Twin (Beta Version).** A Beta version of the Digital Twin platform containing results and datasets of the 4 RMs.
- **D8: Second Progress Report.** Second year progress report of the flagship project.
- **D9: Second Dataset Delivery.** Second delivery of an integrated dataset containing data from the 4 RMs.

Participation to international conferences:

- [SDEWES 2024](#)
- [IBPC 2024](#)

Datasets

- [Integrated Dataset of the Four Research Module.](#)
- [Co-Simulation Platform – Example of use](#)

Deviations (if applicable):

Activities related to **Objective 1 – Task 3: Development and integration of a water multi-reservoir model for the co-simulation platform at daily /hourly scale** and **Objective 2 – Task 1: Development of the Orco Valley Reservoirs network and evaluation of the water need for hydro-potable service** have been moved to Research Module 4 since it was deemed necessary and reasonable to include all the activities related to “water” domain in the same research module.

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

N/A

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

The objectives for the next reporting period focus on advancing the capabilities of the proposed co-simulation architecture. Specifically, the following enhancements will be introduced:

- Extension with a digital real-time simulator for electric systems, enabling detailed simulation of specific subsystems within the energy community.
- Development of a robust model for Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS), which are essential for Renewable Energy Communities (RECs). Coupling BESS with PV systems can significantly enhance the self-consumption of prosumers.
- Introduction of an Energy Management System (EMS) module for heating systems, allowing the configuration of various control strategies at both the single building and district levels.
- Introduction of an EMS module for BESS, enabling better integration and optimization of battery storage within the energy community.

These advancements in the co-simulation architecture will be tested in the Frassinetto case study, providing meaningful results to be presented. In particular simple rule-based control strategy will be tested within the developed EMS modules.

1.2.2 Research Module 3

Research Module n.3	Start month: 1				End month: 36			
Title: Risk-resilient Energy and Water Infrastructures								
Location in Mezzogiorno: Y								
RM Leader	POLITO				Prof. Daniele Peila			
Partners involved	POLITO	UNITO	LINKS	UNIBAS	FMS			
Type of action:	Industrial Research							
Effort in person/months:	3.6	0.2	2.8	3.2	2.2			
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):								
<p>Water adduction, water collected in reservoirs and energy transmission network in mountain environments are typically subject to multiple natural hazards such as landslides, accelerated soil erosion, earthquakes, snow avalanches, glacial collapse, river floods, which can induce critical interruption and/or reduced efficiency in the services provided by the utility companies. Through digitalization, infrastructure systems can become more resilient, as well as provide rapid, accurate asset conditions assessments to support decision-making and adaptation. Droughts as well are challenging energy and water supply utilities. Digitalization can help in a better knowledge of the effects of these hazards and the management of their effects also taking into account the climate change effect.</p>								
Summary of the activities envisaged for the period detailing the contribution by each Partner/Research Team for each objective (provide measurable indicators, if available):								
Objective 1 - Avalanches								
Task 1 - Study of areas subject to avalanches (avalanche dynamics & detachment point)								
<p>The dynamic of avalanches was studied using the open-access code "Avaframe" and a DTM as input data. A specific back-analysis of an event that occurred in Valsarvarance (AO) on 08/01/2018 that damaged a high-tension pylon was carried out. Many case histories have been reported and analysed to understand the interaction between the avalanche flow and the electricity pylons. Simulations of the impact of an avalanche on an energy pole have been carried out, and the interpretation is under development to define a vulnerability chart of these infrastructures. A study of the detachment point related to the slope dip has been carried out regarding relevant case histories in Piedmont and Aosta Valley (database of ARPA Piemonte and Comando Truppe Alpine-Servizio Meteomont). The analysis was developed based on the shapefile of the detachment areas of 65 events, considering the upper third of each avalanche basin in the Aosta Valley Catasto Regionale Valanghe.</p> <p>In the last semester, the work was concentrated on the automatic definition of the avalanche probable release areas (PRA), finding by the combination of selected ranges of slope, plan</p>								

curvature and vector terrain ruggedness. It was also studied the possible protective action of the forest, thanks to its stabilizing action, within certain limits, on the snowpack and its capacity to regulate snowfall or the formation of wind deposits.

For this activity it was used the Satellite images from the Copernicus portfolio.

The avalanche-protection effects were divided into three classes related to tree crown cover density (TCD) and the Small Woody Features (HRL) obtaining different scenarios:

- PRA raster for the EXTREME SCENARIO in which only protection forest with a canopy cover (TCD) > 50% has an excellent protective effect;
- PRA raster for the INTERMEDIATE SCENARIO in which the sparse forest contributes to the avalanche protective effect with the dense forest (TCD > 30%);
- PRA raster for the FREQUENT SCENARIO in which the sparse forest and patchy structures of trees or scrubs also somehow contribute to the avalanche protective effect with the dense forest (TCD > 30% + HRL).

On these three new rasters, the majority filter and a smoothing process were applied and were removed the polygons with areas < 1.500 m² and "holes" with areas < 2.500 m² to obtain perimeters as realistic as possible as shown in the following figures.

Figure 45 - From PRAs raster (left) to PRAs shapefiles (right)

The PRAs are subdivided into smaller PRAs thanks to the application of the Drainage Network – Watershed areas tool.

Each shapefile of the identified PRAs was tested according to the three reference scenarios.

For this statistical characterization, four steepness classes were considered: (unsteep < 30°; steep between 30° and 35°; very steep between 35° and 40°; extremely steep > 40°) and PRA magnitude classes (size of release area): large (PRA > 100.000 m²), medium (50.000 m² < PRA < 100.000 m²) and small (PRA < 50.000 m²).

To simplify the results visualization, the results of the statistical analysis conducted on PRAs have been associated with the perimeter of the event.

The results do not change significantly between the three scenario (frequent, intermediate and extreme) results except for a slight increase in planar curvature and ruggedness in the very and extremely steep classes. In contrast, the correlation between slope classes and release elevations appears to have a similar but opposite trend.

In Aosta Valley Region, for the frequent and intermediate scenario, 85% of the PRAs are classifiable as true positives while only 15% are false negatives. The extreme scenario shows that 89% of the PRAs are classifiable as true positives while only 11% are false negatives.

Figure 46 - BoxPlot of the PRAs identified for the extreme scenario according to the slope classes: mean elevation, planar curvature and vector terrain ruggedness. The map shows the PRA obtained for the extreme scenario.

The PRAs were also analyzed according to the area size classified into three classes: large PRA > 100.000 m², medium PRA (between 50.000 m² and 100.000 m²); and small PRA < 50.000 m². For the Valle d'Aosta Region, for all three scenarios (extreme, intermediate and frequent), numerically, 91% of PRAs are small, 7% medium and 3% large. Compared to the total area occupied by the PRAs, small PRAs cover 54%, medium 26% and large 21%.

The activities described above were carried out in collaboration with AINEVA (Dott. Igor Chiambretti) and ARPA Piemonte (Dott. Luca Lanteri).

The monitoring of the open channel of the CVA hydroelectric power plant of Chavonne is continued also comparing the obtained data with those of the satellite Cosmic Rays and with the results of the monitoring of soil moisture, soil temperature and soil pressure head in the slope

The analysis of three meteo stations in the area to define risk threshold avalanche has been carried out.

A photo surveying on spring avalanches in the Nivolet area occurred in the spring 2017-18 where some avalanches have damaged or demolished some high tension poles of Terna.

In collaboration with CVA it has been installed a network of three sites, each one with sensors at 10, 20 and 40 cm depth. The objective is to establish a network of sites in order to provide managers with information in relation to thresholds to be evaluated. Also a small number of houses is below the open channel.

Recently a Cosmic Ray apparatus has been bought by CVA for monitoring the soil moisture on a larger area than the point sensors, and comparisons are underway.

Data from sensors have been developed in CSV format.

Figure 47 - View of an installation site of the sensors monitoring of soil moisture, soil temperature and soil pressure

Partner/Research teams: POLITO, UNITO, FMS

Task 2 - Hazard condition of energetic Infrastructures

2.1 Snow Avalanches

A correlation between the static variables (geological) and the dynamic variables (mainly linked with the meteorological conditions) was developed to define instability indexes. These indexes are used in GIS mapping to assess hazard conditions with reference to energetic infrastructure networks. The results from Task1-Objective1 will be indispensable for correctly identifying energy infrastructures at risk and defining their risk level.

The activities in the last period was devoted to the study of the vulnerability of power transmission lines exposed to dry snow avalanches, particularly aiming to define fragility curves for typical support structures. Both poles and transmission towers, which are critical for electricity supply in remote areas, have been analyzed. These structures are prone to damage from avalanches, which exert dynamic forces through their dense core and powder cloud components. The avalanche core, composed of compacted snow, moves along the terrain, while the airborne powder cloud can impact higher sections of the structures. In detail, the analysis refers to the effect of the dense component on the structural members of a tower (see an example in Figure 48)

The avalanche action on the structure consists in a uniformly distributed pressure acting on the bottom at various heights. To account for the variability in the avalanche conditions, a parametric analysis has been performed.

The tests consist in the progressive increase of the pressure and the continuous monitoring of the stresses in the members and the displacements of the lowest nodes of the tower.

A sub-structure model of the bottom part, i.e. the “Considered region”. This solution speeds up the analysis time and allows to perform a full parametric analysis with a reasonable computational effort.

Figure 48 - View of a transmission tower (on the left); Fragility curves for different flow depths (on the right)

To account for the variability of the possible tower structures, the sample structure has been sketched in plan with different scaling factors. As the impact direction is not known a priori, 11 different load cases, corresponding to frontal, lateral or inclined impacts have been simulated. All the analysis has been done in a FEM environment thanks to Abaqus CAE software.

A non-linear analysis accounting for material plastic behavior has been set and the results have highlighted interesting outcomes. The failure of the system has been quantified based on geometrical and mechanical threshold exceedance during the pushover analysis. By comparing the various simulated cases (scaling and impact orientation), the fragility curves have been obtained. The crosses (x) in the plot indicate the simulations, while the continuous lines are the log normal distributions that best fit the data obtained from the numerical models.

In the semester has been continued the analysis of the data included in the “catasto valanghe” of VdA (in cooperation with struttura assetto idrogeologico dei bacini montani and FMS) and of Piedmont (in cooperation with ARPA – Piemonte) and the data contained in the “Monografia militare delle valanghe” (in cooperation with Comando Truppe Alpine-Servizio Meteomont). The obtained data for Piedmont and for the case study of Valli Orco e Soana have been correlated with the distribution of the electric distribution infrastructures to define the possible interferences. These results are under development also within a MSc thesis in “Scienze e Tecnologie dei Sistemi e Territori Forestali”. The analysis of this dataset is under development. The first results highlight that the interaction between the network of electricity distribution and the avalanche potentially impacted areas in Piedmont are more that 3000. In the case study of

Valli Orco and Soana there are 6 avalanche sites that interact with the electric distribution network while if considering the poles 3 sites have to be considered.

Partner/Research teams: POLITO, UNITO, FMS

2.2 Glacier

A database of ice avalanches in Aosta Valley and the Alps (including information on the collapsed volume and angle of reach) has been developed. All the water intake and hydroelectric plans of CVA on Aosta Valley have been collected to establish a methodology for risk assessment related to the impact of ice collapses on these infrastructures. The development of detailed maps of the potential risk induced by glacial collapse in Aosta Valley is in progress.

Glacier of Planpincieux was selected as case study. A database of ice avalanche events from this glacier was created, considering the volumes and the collapse speed, as well as a map of the deposits. A specific script that automatically creates the DTM of the release area and impact area was explicitly developed to use it as input for the preprocessing data using `r.avaflow`, an open-source software for the simulation of cascading mass flows.

The activities focused on a study case in Aosta Valley. The Planpincieux Glacier was the focus of an extensive study to understand the risks associated with possible ice avalanches. This glacier, located in the Aosta Valley, has been identified as one of the most vulnerable to glacial detachment phenomena. Such detachments pose a threat not only to the integrity of the territory, but also to the infrastructure and local populations.

To address this challenge, a database has been created that collects information on ice avalanche events, with a focus on the volumes and distance covered by glacial detachments. These data were obtained from various monitoring systems and from the analysis of the mapping of deposits. This work represents a crucial step in better understanding glacier dynamics and preventing potential natural disasters.

An important part of the study involved the use of open-source software for the simulation of cascading mass flows. In particular, an opposite script was created to pre-process the data and make it possible to use the `r.avaflow` software. This program makes it possible to accurately simulate the movements of ice masses, enabling better prediction of impact areas and potential damage.

In parallel, tests were conducted with the `r.randomwalk` software to simulate the dynamics of ice flows. These tests proved to be crucial for understanding how ice avalanches can propagate, and which areas are most at risk. Thanks to these simulations, it is possible to develop more effective mitigation strategies and plan early interventions to minimize damage.

In addition to the technical aspects, historical research was carried out on the ice avalanches that affected the Aosta Valley and the Alps. This research made it possible to further enrich the

database with valuable information on past events, including the release volume and propagation angle of the avalanches.

Figure 49 - Example of Interference map between ice avalanches and critical infrastructure

Risk analysis is another essential component of the project therefore punctual shapefiles locating all the intake works and hydroelectric power plants managed by the CVA (Compagnia Valdostana delle Acque) were analysed. This made it possible to conduct a qualitative assessment of the risk of interference between glacial detachments and these critical infrastructures

Two sites of particular interest were identified, where the risk of interference is considered to be highest. The details of these sites were forwarded to the Politecnico di Torino, which will develop modelling surveys to measure the volumes of ice present on the terrain. These surveys will contribute to a better understanding of glacial dynamics and potential threats to local infrastructure.

Partner/Research teams: FMS

Objective 2 - Slope stability

Task 1 - Impact of climate change on slope stability in Alpine environment.

Definition of the static variables (geological and structural) and meteo conditions to be used as indicators of instability. Application of the study to the Monte Rosa area. Collection of meteorological data (temperature and rain days). Creation of a dataset of landslides in Aosta valley considering and selecting the data needed for the research (542 data were selected). The data related TWI (Topographic Wetness Index), SPI (Stream Power Index) e STI (Sediment Transport Index) have been collected, and the relationship with the stability of the slopes has been assessed. The model has been developed using the algorithm "XGBoost".

Since landslide susceptibility maps (LSM) play a crucial role in various contexts, such as aiding in land use planning, devising strategies for mitigation, and establishing early warning systems in the research these maps must be developed. These maps are developed within a Geographic Information System (GIS) integrated environment are crucial in developing disaster prevention measures and mitigating future risks with a specific focus on the risks posed to energy infrastructure in the region as a result of landslides.

Global warming is causing frequency, areal distribution and intensity of precipitations to change while the occurrence of severe rainfalls and snowfalls events has increased. In this framework the need arises to determine susceptibility maps for the future scenarios.

The attention has been focused on landslide susceptibility in the Aosta Valley, Italy, taking into account the influence of climate change.

Machine learning algorithms (Random Forest (RF) and logistic regression (LR)) were employed for this purpose.

The first step of the study developed in the previous semester involved comprehensive data collection. Different parameters (in number of 16) were gathered from online sources and companies operating in the area: "Elevation," "Distance to roads," "Distance to faults," "Lithology," "NDVI," "Land cover," "Aspect," "Slope," "SPI," "STI," "TWI," "Precipitation," "Temperature," "Soil type," "Plan curvature," and "Profile curvature."

After conducting initial analyses, in the second semester some parameters were removed for the

calculations: "Distance to roads" was excluded to prevent the algorithm from becoming overly dependent on road locations, and since the region is not seismically active, "Distance to faults" was also eliminated. Additionally, both "Elevation" and "TWI" were dropped due to their multicollinearity effects on the model.

Next, a dataset for "Precipitation" and "Temperature" was prepared, consisting of daily maps from 2003 to 2022. These data were then averaged annually.

In the considered semester the research has arrived to develop a single landslide susceptibility map (LSM) that was generated for the period 2003-2022.

Figure 50 - LSM for 2003-2022 (left image); LSM for February 2003-2022 (center); LMS for February 2021-2040 (right).

In the considered semester, since the study aims to examine the impacts of climate change on landslides, climatic data must be analyzed in more detailed timeframes rather than annual averages, monthly data were used: average values were calculated for temperature, and cumulative averages for precipitation. Thanks to this consideration new maps has been developed for the other months, as well as for the next 20 years.

Partner/Research teams: POLITO, UNITO

Task 2 - Wire drapery mesh and rockfall protection embankment

It has been studied the frame for the design and development of a digital tool for assessing the state of degradation of wire mesh net fences.

The development of the digital tool is in an advanced level.

It has been based on a two steps:

- a tool based on a mobile device to be used on site for site inspection
- a tool based on a back office development that compute the indicators of the state of deterioration of the net fence and create a data-set of the net fences positions.

Tests of two reinforced rockfall embankments at a reduced scale. The tests were carried out on a scaled embankment in September 2024. The experimental campaign aimed to reproduce and analyze the instant of collapse of a reinforced rockfall protection embankment (RE-RPE) in function of two specific reinforcement technologies: Terramesh system from Maccaferri, which includes the use of clips as joint punctual elements among the elements, and a wraparound system with extruded unidirectional HDPE geogrid. In particular, to identify the geometric configuration preceding the collapse condition and provide a definition of RE-RPE collapse not currently available in literature.

On the basis of the obtained results a preliminary draft of the proposal for a patent of an embankment has been set up and is presently under analysis and final definition.

The tests were carried out following this geometrical scheme

Figure 51 - Cross section of the RE-RPEs with scale factor $\lambda=5$

The two RE-RPEs to be tested were built confined between two walls of concrete blocks. Wooden frames with a geometry equal to the cross section of the RE-RPE were installed on them.

Then, the 8 layers of the embankment were assembled using formworks made from wooden boards fixed to the frames. These formworks were removed at the end of the layer construction.

Each layer of the RE-RPE were built with the following procedure

Positioning of the scaled reinforcement with a width equal to 70 cm, so that each layer had exactly 6 reinforcing panels to cover the 4 m wide and a slight overlapping.

Installation of the scaled formworks and of a geotextile only in the side bank zones to prevent the soil leakage. Filling of the layer with the selected soil, levelling to reach 15 cm (height of each layer) and compaction with vibrating plate.

Closure of the layer with the wrapping of the reinforcement equal to 20 cm.

In the case of RE-RPE with Terramesh, clips spaced 5 cm were used to simulate the correct system configuration: this involves joining the adjacent reinforcement panels and the adjacent formworks in 4 directions. Obviously, also the clips properties were been appropriately scaled.

The RE-RPEs were stressed by a circular steel plate with a diameter of 30 cm, which was pushed at mid height against the upstream bank to simulate the crater created by an impact block and, consequently, recreate the deformative state that this causes on the whole structure. The thrust operation was carried out by a long stroke hydraulic jack fitted during the test with various extension cables. The jack was fixed to a concrete block. The test continued until the volume affected by the detected collapsed.

The following measurements were taken during the tests: The time pressure of the hydraulic jack and, consequently, the force of thrust; the jack displacement; the deformation of the downstream bank of the embankments were measured by continuous photogrammetric network.

Figure 52 - Set-up of the trust system and of the photogrammetrical network.

The evolution of the resistant mechanism in the case of reinforced with a wrap-around geogrid system and with Terramesh system was studied.

From the images it can be seen that the mechanism does not seem to change significantly either by the volume of soil being extruded downstream or by the clearly visible cracking pattern in the crest.

Further numerical back-analysis analyses, to be used as a comparison with the photogrammetric survey, are currently being developed.

A photo surveying on rock fall events occurred in the Mont Avic area (VdA) that impacted some protection devices used to protect high tension poles has been carried out.

Partner/Research teams: POLITO, UNITO, LINKS

Objective 3 - Stability of earth dams reservoirs

Task 1 – Testing procedure.

In the semester the reservoir of Fourcare in Val d'AYas (VdA) has been monitored in continuous using this example as a pilot test to check the application of geophysical methodologies (seismic and electric) to analyze the behavior of the earth dam.

The following main tasks were studied:

- geomatic characterization using lidar on drones to develop a 3D model of the reservoir
- analysis of the geophysical data (seismic and electric) of the earth dam to obtain 2D cross vertical section in a way to obtain 2D model of the mechanical behavior of the whole system: the mechanical moduli and the Poisson coefficient; the evaluation of the electrical resistivity to assess the presence of filtration water inside the earth dam;
- geophysical monitoring of the embankments, according to
 - Time-lapse geoelectrical monitoring according to the installation of a series of electrodes on the downstream slope of the embankment, by controlling remotely the energization and the data acquisition; this monitoring allowed to study the behavior of electrical resistivity over time, that could be related to the variation of soil moisture/water content of the embankment; in parallel a procedures for the processing of the geoelectric tomography data acquired in time lapse modality (with daily frequency) was implemented;
 - microseismic monitoring, carried out with 3 accelerometric stations, aimed to detect the seismic microtremors; this monitoring allows to estimate the response of the system to deformation and filtration phenomena.

The following paragraphs describe the installation of the geophysical equipment and the main results achieved for the characterization of the embankment; the analysis of the geoelectric and microtremor monitoring is still under process.

The 3D image of the embankment was already developed, and it is given in geotiff format (annexed).

Task 1.1 – Disposal of geophysical devices

The following figure shows the location of the electrodes used for the 6 electrical tomography lines and the seismic tomography lines for the detection of velocity of compressional waves and shear waves. The position of the fixed seismic instrumentation (accelerometric station for microtremor detection) and the position of the electrodes for the time-lapse monitoring of the electrical resistivity values are also given.

Figure 53 - position of the sensors for the electrical resistivity tomographic section (circles); the yellow circles refer to the permanent electrode installed for the time-lapse electrical resistivity monitoring (since October 2023); triangles refer to the position of seismic sensors for the tomographies of the velocity of compressional waves and measurements of surface waves for the detection of shear waves velocity; the same sensors were used for recording the seismic ambient noise.

The results of the active and passive seismic characterization are herein reported; in particular, with reference to the figure below, the vertical section of the distribution of the velocity of the compressional and shear waves velocity (seismic section S1-S2) is reported. The distribution of the Poisson coefficient is obtained from the velocity sections of the shear and compressional waves.

In the lower part of figure below, the results of the passive seismic measurements (ambient noise) relating to the same sensors of the S1 and S2 tomographic lines are reported. The image in figure below identifies the distribution of noise at different frequencies (in the range between 10 Hz and 30 Hz) for the whole vertical section. The peak values are identified in the central part of the section (red hot-spot) and they detect a potential region of higher seismic noise within the embankment. Figure below also reproduces the in-depth conversion of the frequency response, to better detect the depth of the occurrence of the main anomalies.

Figure 54 - Results of seismic characterization along the S1-S2 sections; starting from the bottom a) ambient noise section; b) main frequencies of microseismic noise; c) vertical distribution section of the Poisson coefficient; d) vertical section of the shear wave velocity (S waves, values in m/s); e) vertical section of the compressional wave velocity (P waves, values in m/s).

Partner/Research teams: POLITO

Task 1.2 – Analysis of seismic and electrical behaviour

The seismic sections of P and S wave velocity show with good resolution the transition between the material of the embankment (dam body) and the “bedrock” on which the dam is set; in particular, the increasing values of P and S waves velocity with depth are in agreement with the degree of compaction of the material, that increases with the depth.

The velocity values of the compressional wave velocity at the depth between 15 m and 20 m w can be associated with an increase in water saturation in that region of the earth-dam, as also shown in the section of the Poisson coefficient. The values of the Poisson coefficient, between 0.4 and 0.45, at deeper level in the terminal part of the section of the Poisson coefficient are related to the increase in saturation in water.

The distribution of the Poisson coefficient allows us also to detect the boundary between the earth-dam body and the bedrock, highlighted in Figure 54.c by the dotted line in red.

It should also be noted that peaks of the noise distribution, where the observed maxima are aligned precisely in correspondence with the boundary between low and high velocity region of the P wave velocity distribution.

Partner/Research teams: POLITO

Objective 4 - Landslides

Task 1 – Remote sensing detection.

Compilation and analysis of existing remote sensing data and methodologies for landslide detection. Identification of key spectral indices and terrain parameters influential in landslide occurrence. Application of the initial findings to the regions of Piedmont and Valle d'Aosta. Development and calibration of a predictive model integrating Earth Observation (EO) data with real-time environmental monitoring to enhance landslide delineation capabilities. This task is currently underway with preliminary models showing potential in detecting recent landslides, though further refinement is needed to improve accuracy and reliability.

A novel deep learning model has been developed for the task of automatic landslide delineation. The model frames the problem as a change detection task: given a pair of Sentinel-2 L2A images (resolution: 10 m/px), taken respectively before and after a landslide-triggering event, the model outputs a binary segmentation mask delineating landslides which are visible in the “post” image but not in the “pre” image.

To train this model, it has been retrieved, harmonized and combined several open-access landslide inventories from different ecoregions of the world, constructing a global and heterogeneous landslide database whose size is in the order of tens of thousands manually validated landslides. The inventory available in the research group data base encompasses landslides of different sizes, from very small (in the range of 100 m²) to very large (in the range of 100,000 m²), and triggered by different catastrophic events, such as earthquakes and heavy rainfall.

The harmonized landslide inventory was used to retrieve pre- and post-landslide Sentinel-2 image pairs at each landslide location, which were then used to train the landslide delineation model. Thanks to the inventory's diverseness and visual heterogeneity, the model could achieve sufficiently robust performances, even on smaller-scale landslides located in parts of the world which were not taken into consideration for the training, and despite the medium spatial resolution offered by Sentinel-2 images.

The model was applied on three landslide events located in Piedmont and Valle d'Aosta. Results are visualized and briefly discussed hereafter.

Landslide in Luzzogno (VB), occurred on 01-04-2024 Source: rainews.it

Figure 55 - Landslide in Luzzogno (VB) as seen by Sentinel-2. (left) pre-event image (19-04-2023), (right) post-event image (13-04-2024), with detail on the model's output delineation mask (in red)

This landslide, occurred near the town of Luzzogno (VB), consisted of a long but narrow flow of debris along a hillside escarpment. Despite the model was not able to delineate the whole extension of the landslide (probably due to its peculiar narrowness), it succeeded in locating the landslide in the point of its maximum width.

Landslide in Limone Piemonte (CN), occurred on 02-10-2020 Source: vigilfuoco.tv

Figure 56 - Landslide in Limone Piemonte (CN) as seen by Sentinel-2. (left) pre-event image (02-10-2019), (right) post-event image (03-10-2020), with detail on the model's output delineation mask (in red)

Multiple landslides occurred as a result of flooding in the Limone Piemonte (CN) area. In the Sentinel-2 post-event image, landslide subsidence caused by the overflow of the Vermenagna stream is clearly visible along the banks of the creek. Such subsidence areas have been successfully detected by our landslide delineation model.

Landslide in Meyen (AO), occurred on 05-08-2022 Source: rainews.it

Figure 57 - Landslide in Meyen (AO) as seen by Sentinel-2. (left) pre-event image (18-07-2022), (right) post-event image (01-09-2022), with detail on the model's output delineation mask (in red)

A heavy rainfall event caused the overflow of the Rochefort stream, near the hamlet of Meyen (AO). A Sentinel-2 image taken after the event clearly shows traces of the large debris flow which hit the area. The landslide delineation model was able to locate the areas of maximum extension of the landslide events. Interestingly, a land scar caused by a past landslide is visible in the pre-event S2 image, but it has not been detected by the model. This behavior was expected, as the model has been trained to detect only newly-occurred landslides with respect to the given pre-event image.

Partner/Research teams: LINKS

Outputs so far:

5 publication have been published so far.

Journal Publications (see Table 8 for more detail)

- M. Marchelli, A. Pol, D. Peila, F. Gabrieli (2023) [Towards a Hybrid Design Approach of Anchored Drapery Systems](#), Geosciences 2023, 13(5), 147
- Marchelli M., Peila D., Giacomini A. (2023) [Rockfall in open pit mines: management of the pit geometry and protection measure design](#), International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences, 170, 105551
- Marchelli M., Coltrinari G., Degan G. A., Peila D. (2023) [Toward a procedure to manage safety on construction sites of rockfall protective measures](#), Safety Science 168, 106307

Publication in conference proceeding (see Table 8 for more detail)

- Bovet Eloise, De Biagi Valerio, Durand Nathalie, Debernardi Andrea, Roveyaz Simone (2023) [A multilevel framework for the management of energy infrastructures involved by avalanches](#), ISSW 2023, Bend (Oregon)

- Monopoli T., Montello F., Rossi C. "[Landslide mapping from Sentinel-2 imagery through change detection](#)", IEEE 2024

Deliverables (see Table 4 for more detail)

- **D3: Geodatabase Structure.** Definition of the Geodatabase structure for the Digital Twin Implementation.
- **D4: First Progress Report.** First year progress report of the flagship project.
- **D5: First Dataset Delivery.** First delivery of an integrated dataset containing data from the 4 RMs.
- **D6: Digital Twin (Beta Version).** A Beta version of the Digital Twin platform containing results and datasets of the 4 RMs.
- **D8: Second Progress Report.** Second year progress report of the flagship project.
- **D9: Second Dataset Delivery.** Second delivery of an integrated dataset containing data from the 4 RMs.

Participation to international conferences:

- ISSW2023
- IEEE 2024
- ISSW2024
- 4th Macao International Conference on smart city technologies, Macao (2024)

Reports

- [Report on the procedures for the geophysical testing of rockfall embankments](#)
- [Report on the results of the small-scale tests on rockfall embankments \(report 1 and 2\)](#)
- [Geophysical survey – "Cime Bianche Lake"](#)

Datasets

- [Integrated Dataset of the Four Research Module.](#)

IPR

- A patent proposal about a mass transport detection system and related detection procedure was filed on 7/12/2022 successfully from the search report.

Results:

Objective 1 - Avalanches

Task 1 - Study of areas subject to avalanches: avalanche dynamic and detachment point

Procedure for the automatic definition of the avalanche probable release areas (PRA), finding by the combination of selected ranges of slope, plan curvature and vector terrain ruggedness.

A photo surveying on spring avalanches in the Nivolet area occurred in the spring 2017-18

The data from sensors have been collected in CSV format.

Task 2 - Hazard condition of energetic Infrastructures

2.1 Snow Avalanches

The research conducted has allowed to reach the following main objectives in the semester:

Development of fragility curves of energetic infrastructures

2.2 Glacier

The research conducted has allowed to reach the following main objectives in the semester:

Creation of a database that collects information on ice avalanche events, with a focus on the volumes and distance covered by glacial detachments.

Development a qualitative assessment of the risk of interference between glacial detachments and these critical infrastructures

Objective 2 - Slope stability

Task 1 - Impact of climate change on slope stability in Alpine environment.

Generation of landslide susceptibility maps (LSMs) for each month of the year.

Task 2 - Wire drapery mesh and rockfall protection embankment

Understanding of the resistant mechanisms of Reinforced Embankments with the two different reinforcement systems.

Validation of the GRE test methodology. The same mechanism of sliding downstream of the layers involved observed in the full-scale tests of Peila et al. 2007 was obtained. The numerical model of the systems studied with the software Abaqus/CAE are in good agreement with those measured.

Definition of a preliminary proposal of a patent (presently under development and check of validity)

Objective 3- Stability of earth dams reservoirs

Task 1 - Testing procedure.

Development of seismic and electrical configuration array for detection of mechanical properties and monitoring of water content distribution within the earth-dam

Objective 4- Landslides

Task 1 – Remote sensing detection.

A novel deep learning model has been developed for the task of automatic landslide delineation

Deviations (if applicable):

N/A

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

- Sony 7C camera with 24-70 and 70.-200 lenses
- Development of an app for the management of the damages of net fences
- Development and assistance for the construction of test protection embankments

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

Objective 1 - Avalanches

Task 1 - Study of areas subject to avalanches

- The PRAs would be used in the next period as input of avalanche dynamics models to evaluate the interaction between the avalanches and the electricity distribution network.
- The PRAs are under validation thanks a comparison with real events. This activity will be finalized in next semester

Task 2 - Hazard condition of energetic Infrastructures

2.1 Snow Avalanches

- Development of a paper to be submitted to the ASCE Journal of the Performance of Constructed Facilities
- Development of a report of the computed fragility curves
- To continue the detection of the parameters obtained by the installed sensors

2.2 Glacier

During this semester two sites of particular interest were identified, where the risk of interference is considered to be highest. The details of these sites were forwarded to the Politecnico di Torino, which will develop a modelling to evaluate the volumes of ice present on the terrain. These surveys will contribute to a better understanding of glacial dynamics and potential threats to local infrastructure.

Objective 2 - Slope stability

Task 1 - Impact of climate change on slope stability in Alpine environment.

- Overlaying the maps related to landslides to identify infrastructures that may be at risk in the area.

- Development of a dataset for "Precipitation" and "Temperature" with the daily maps from 2003 to 2022.

Task 2 - Wire drapery mesh and rockfall protection embankment

- Complete the development of the digital tool for management of net fences and test it
- Submit an international paper on rockfall on the test on embankments
- Finalize the patent on the embankments to protect punctual elements

Objective3

Task1

- Definition of the protocol for the interpretation of the seismic and electrical resistivity tomography plus ambient noise monitoring to characterize the earth-dam.
- Development of the protocol for interpretation of time-lapse geoelectrical monitoring to be related to the temporal changes of water content within the earth-dam
- Processing of the 3D model of the earth-dam for the digital twin of the system

Objective4

Task1

- Development of new test on other landslides

1.2.2 Research Module 4

Research Module n.4	Start month: 1	End month: 36
Title: Smart Energy and Water Distribution Systems		
Location in Mezzogiorno: N		
RM Leader	POLITO	Prof. Davide Poggi
Partners involved	POLITO	
Type of action:	Industrial Research	
Effort in person/months:	2.5	
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):		
<p>The increasing water demand for hydropower and the impact of climate change on the availability of water requires a dramatic re-thinking how to keep the lights (and the taps) on, while both are making the best use of new energy (and water) sources and keeping infrastructure costs down. Instead of only extending and reinforcing physical infrastructure, which is extremely costly and disruptive to local communities, new management policies and systems are needed to arrive at decisions that narrow the discrepancies between stakeholders (i.e. energy producers, drinking water suppliers and irrigation consortia). To support these decision-making approaches, it is necessary to implement a better knowledge of the systems that use the water resource at the basin scale. Complementary, IT solutions must be developed, adding communication, sensors, and automation, allowing distribution-system operators to actively manage the varying generation and demand. This combination of solutions is what is commonly referred to as a smart grid. Digitalization of the energy and water distribution networks will prospectively increase the security of supply, improve the quality of service, and better respond to demand from customers.</p>		
Summary of the activities envisaged for the period detailing the contribution by each Partner/Research Team for each objective (provide measurable indicators, if available):		
<p>Objective1 - Digital models of the transmission and distribution networks and innovative smart-grid solutions.</p> <p>Task 1 - Mapping of major transmission and distribution infrastructure.</p> <p>Activities focused on the collection of geo-referenced data to complete the GIS mapping of the basin chosen as a case study for the implementation of the Digital Twin: the Orco Valley. Mapping of reservoirs, intakes and releases. Construction of a script to automate the definition of associated basins using GIS tool (GRASS GIS).</p>		

Task 2 – Investigation of the available data network at the basin scale.

In collaboration with RM1, all ARPA monitoring stations located in the Orco Valley area were mapped and geo-referenced. Historical data were stored up to the time present in the dataset described in Table 6. Identification of the water intake and return network along the basin. Construction of a logical interconnection network between each intake and its downstream return works required for task 2 of the objective 2.

Partner/Research Team: POLITO

Objective2 - Innovative solutions for increasing and better managing the water storage capacity and energy production.

Task 1 - Water availability.

1.1 Flow Duration Curves (FDC)

Calculation of the Orco Valley hydrographic network and estimation of flow duration curves (FDC) at each node by Regionalization method. The activities involved the use of GIS tools for watershed analysis, identification of the hydrographic network, and sub-basins related to each node in the network. Additional applications developed in R, MatLAB, and Python allowed the identification of the network of intakes and returns present in the sub-basins as well as the calculation of the new ecological runoff (replacing the previous DMV) for each of the nodes in the network. By subtracting from the flow rate value of the natural FDC both the corresponding value of ecological outflow and the non-compensated flow rate (intake-return network), the “final FDC” has been evaluated.

1.2 Effective Flow Rate availability

Calculation of the hydrological runoff by the TUW model using the data identified in Task 1 - Objective 1. The activities involved the identification of the hydrographic network, and sub-basins related to each node in the network. In this way, the intake/return, runoff, and ecological runoff data allowed the estimation of the available volume of water. This step is crucial for determining the inputs to the model described in Task 3 – Objective 2 to be applied to the case study of the Orco Valley.

Partner/Research Team: POLITO

Task 2 – Energy potential

2.1 Hydropower potential

Starting from the results of Task 1.1 regarding water resource availability, the hydroelectric potential was estimated along the entire catchment network of the Orco Valley basin. First, an application was developed in R to determine the maximum geodetic head available within a

given distance from the point considered. In this first phase, 3 different distances of 1Km, 2.5Km, and 5Km were investigated for each point of the hydrographic network. Figure 58 shows an example of the results obtained.

Figure 58 - Distribution of the local maximum geodetic head H over a 1km distance.

In the second phase, a Matlab model has been developed in order to evaluate the value of energy that can be produced in each node of the network. To do this, the flow rate value was defined in the initial phase, as the annual average flow rate value that can be derived in that node and the efficiency value of the hypothetical hydroelectric plant was set to 1.

These values, including the distance of the geodetic head, in a subsequent implementation of the digital tool, will be editable by the user allowing different analyses to be performed.

2.2 Photovoltaic potential

Extrapolation of solar irradiance data over the Orco Valley basin at 100m resolution from the PVGIS-SARAH2 dataset for further investigation about the photovoltaic potential.

2.3 Energy Demand

The current energy demand, in terms of the hydroelectric energy to be produced, has been assumed by considering the historical production data of the Orco Valley Power Plants published by Iren, which is the company that currently has the dam system (Figure 3) under concession.

To assess the change in energy demand assuming future scenarios that might involve the construction of new reservoirs, the watershed energy potential has been estimated by determining the hydrodynamic curve of the basin, proposed by Ganassini, Esemplio di utilizzazione completa delle disponibilità idroelettriche di un bacino imbrifero alpino. L'Elettrotecnica. 1929.

This diagram, which is helpful in the small-extension watershed in which the area could be considered proportional to the run-off, presents the river elevation on the y-axis and the relative catchment area on the x-axis. It is useful because the area of the diagram (DH X S) bounded by the difference between the intake elevation and the plant elevation (DH) and the catchment area described by the intake elevation (S) is proportional to the power of the plant.

Partner/Research Team: POLITO

Task 3 – Implementation of an Integrated Watershed model of the Orco valley.

A basin-scale multi – models' tool for simulation and optimization of water resource management has been theorized and it is in an advanced stage of development. The Python-based, open-source tool has a modular structure: each block represents a model that can be written in different programming languages. A schematic representation of the comprehensive structure of the Integrated tool is shown in Figure 59 below. The present multi-models' tool application is used to allow an optimal use of the resources of the Orco Valley.

Figure 59 - Schematic representation of the Integrated Watershed Model

In the current section, a general overview of methods implemented for the development of the Orco valley Integrated Watershed framework is reported.

In general, a framework for the integrated assessment of a watershed consists of three main sections (Figure 60). The first section involves actions, which can be either **planning (structural)** or **management (non-structural)** in nature. It is important to distinguish between these two types of actions: **planning (structural)** decisions, which are implemented once and remain, versus **management (non-structural)** decisions, which are dynamic and require periodic adjustments. These actions must be evaluated with the interests of stakeholders in mind and are essential for the implementation of scenarios.

Next is the **modeling section**, where all the elements of the watershed are simulated and analyzed.

Finally, there is an **optimization section**, which considers the interconnected aspects of the watershed, such as water, energy, land use, and ecosystems, to ensure a balanced and efficient management approach.

In particular, all the already developed modeling phases are detailed. Looking at the overall scheme of the Orco Valley system in Figure 61, the modules already implemented are the Watershed General Set-up, the Run-off model, the Reservoir and Intake model, and hydropower model.

Figure 60 General scheme of an Integrated Watershed framework

Figure 61 Orco Valley Modeling Section. Green pop-ups: modeled elements within the basin. Gray pop-ups: elements yet to be modeled. In the background: a map of the Orco Valley and various elements from the GeoPackage to be modeled.

Watershed General Set-up

A preliminary survey of the area is fundamental for proper watershed modeling. Indeed, the framing of the territory makes it possible to identify the hydrological setting and to map the hydraulic works (e.g., reservoirs, intakes). This is necessary to determine the proper inflow in a specific element of the basin model (e.g., a reservoir or a hydropower plant.). Spatial recognition implies that all runoff contributions from releases or subtraction of upstream intakes have already been considered in determining the inflow into, for example, a selected reservoir.

Specifically, the framing of the territory in the present work has been achieved by elaborating spatial data with Python coding.

- Extraction of a sub-basin :

Once all the relevant coordinates have been identified (such as intakes and reservoirs position or sub-basin discharge points), this code returns all vector layers of sub-basins with area calculated in m^2 for each indicated coordinate pair, saving them in the Geopackage file.

The code performs geospatial operations. It was written in Python and run in QGIS.

- Correlation between sub-basins :

The code checks whether a point (which could be a reservoir or an intake) is contained in another sub-basin and, if so, subtracts the area of the point's catchment area from the basin containing it.

This avoids double counting in the water inflow assessment. An example is the evaluation of the water inflow arriving in a reservoir. This could be the sum of different contributions: the outflow of an upstream dam, the river flow, and the intake outflow. If the river flow sub-basin includes the upstream dam catchment area, avoiding the subtraction of the latter would lead to a misjudgment of the inflow.

Reservoir and Intake models

Figure 62 Hydraulic Network of the Orco Valley of the hydroelectric system managed by Iren

A generic 'Reservoir Class' encapsulating the modeling of the reservoir has been Python written.

Firstly, the parameters needed to define the operational rule and physically characterize the reservoir are initialized. These must be provided by the user before starting the simulation. These are: Location name, Maximum volume, Maximum regulation volume, Dead volume, Length of the spillway crest, Ecological run-off, Reservoir storage curve parameters, Inflow and Outflow for that specific simulation interval, Actual storage for that specific simulation interval, Maximum derivable flow rate, and if any, the operating times of upstream releases of the dam.

After that, different attributes and methods are defined for managing water balance and updating water volume and height.

The "update height(self, storage=None)" method calculates the height of the water in the reservoir using the reservoir curve. If no storage-specific value is passed, use actual storage.

The "update volume(self)" method, updates the volume of the reservoir by calculating the net flow rate (inlet flow rate minus outlet flow rate and Ecological run-off) (Equation 1) checking whether the reservoir is full, empty, or under normal conditions, and calculating the spilled flow rates (Equation 2) and water height.

$$\frac{ds}{dt} = Q_{in} - Q_{out} - Q_{spill} - Q_{DE} \quad (1)$$

Where:

- $\frac{ds}{dt}$ is the storage variation
- Q_{in} is the inflow
- Q_{out} is the outflow
- Q_{spill} is the spillway
- Q_{DE} is the ecological Run-off

The equation for the discharge over the spillway crest is given by

$$Q = C * L * H^{\frac{3}{2}} \quad (2)$$

Where:

- Q is the discharge over the weir or spillway crest.
- C is the discharge coefficient, which accounts for energy losses as water enters the spillway, flows through the spillway, and eventually exits the spillway. Typical values range from 2.6 to 4.0 depending upon the shape of the spillway crest.
- L is the length of the spillway crest.
- H is the upstream energy head above the spillway crest.

It returns the current storage, the spilled flow rate, and a data frame containing the calculated data for each time instant.

The “Intake class” represents a generic water intake system with attributes and methods to manage the balance of inflows and outflows, ensuring that the Ecological Runoff (ER) is met. This class is defined similarly to that of reservoir, but with zero storage. The parameters needed to define the operational rule and physically characterize the intake must be provided by the user before starting the simulation. These are: Name of the intake, Inlet flow rate, Flow rate at the outlet, ER: Ecological runoff, that is the minimum flow rate that must be guaranteed downstream of the outlet, Duration of the simulation period, Dictionary containing thresholds for maximum outlets.

The “Update output(self)” calculates the update of the output flow rate based on the input flow rate and ER. For each time instant of the simulation period, it checks whether the net flow rate (inlet flow rate minus outlet flow rate) is less than the ER. If it is, the net flow rate will equal the ER only and there will be no drawdown. If the net flow rate is sufficient to meet the ER, the withdrawable flow rate will be the outflow rate subtracted from the ecological outflow. Returns the newly calculated flow rates.

Hydropower plant model

A class is implemented that calculates hydropower from the head and flow in effective output to the Reservoir or Intake model.

Partner/Research Team: POLITO

Outputs since the start of the RM:

Deliverables *(see Table 4 for more detail)*

- **D3: Geodatabase Structure.** Definition of the Geodatabase structure for the Digital Twin Implementation.
- **D4: First Progress Report.** First year progress report of the flagship project.
- **D5: First Dataset Delivery.** First delivery of an integrated dataset containing data from the 4 RMs.
- **D6: Digital Twin (Beta Version).** A Beta version of the Digital Twin platform containing results and datasets of the 4 RMs.
- **D8: Second Progress Report.** Second year progress report of the flagship project.
- **D9: Second Dataset Delivery.** Second delivery of an integrated dataset containing data from the 4 RMs.

Datasets *(see Section F for more detail)*

- [SUMMER - Flow Duration Curves & Hydropower Potential - RM4](#)

- [Integrated Dataset of the Four Research Module.](#)
- [SUMMER - OrcoValley_Geopackage - RM4](#)

Participation to international conferences:

Results:

Objective 1:

All the geodata (Task 1 and Task 2) related to the Orco Valley have been collected within a unique geopackage (see Figure 3-4 by way of example). In particular, it includes:

- ARPA monitoring networks
- Water intake/returns including the logical interconnection network
- Basin and Sub basin related to each intake and/or reservoir. (With the associated Area)
- Energy transport infrastructure
- Maps of landslide areas
- Maps of buildings and their heights above ground level

Figure 3. Geopackage Orco Valley: By way of example, the geopackage layers of the intakes relating to the Soana valley¹, their relative sub-basins and releases are shown.

Figure 4. Geopackage Orco Valley: By way of example, the geopackage layers of the reservoirs are shown.

Objective 2 – Task1

1.1 Flow Duration Curves (FDC)

Estimation of water availability with flow duration curves calculated on about 4700 nodes of the hydrographic network with a resolution of 100m per cell.

1.2 Effective Rainfall availability

Starting from the geodata structure developed in Objective 1, a methodology to calculate the water flowing within each reservoir has been implemented.

A Python function was developed to correctly verify the actual area over which the runoff should be calculated. In particular for the present case study, The Orco Geopackage was used to check whether upstream of a dam whose runoff is to be calculated, there are other dams or active intakes, thus subtracting the area of their sub-basins. This approach makes it possible to calculate the runoff by considering only the area of the sub-basin downstream of the upstream dams and/or subtracting the runoff taken by any intakes. After determining the correct basin area, it is possible to run the hydrological model (TUW). Specifically, a Python interface has been created to call the calibration and simulation models implemented in R, thereby creating a unified working structure.

This map of the Orco Valley highlights the network of weather stations, including those currently in place and to be installed (Figure 63). The new weather stations, already available and configured, will be installed at sites

agreed upon with the mountain communities (Orco and Soana Valleys and Gran Paradiso) at strategic points both for the following project and for civil protection purposes.

Figure 63 Orco Valley weather stations network

Objective 2 – Task2

2.1 Hydropower potential

Estimation of the hydropower potential network of the Orco Valley calculated over the hydrographic network described above.

2.2 Photovoltaic potential

Maps of monthly average solar irradiance (see figure above).

Monthly sum of the solar radiation energy that hits one square meter of a horizontal plane, measured in kWh/m²

2.3 Energy Demand

To determine the hydrodynamic curve of Orco the hierarchical structure of the river was defined by following the classical stream order (Figure 64). It is a “bottom-up” hierarchy that

assigns the number “1” to the main. The tributaries are assigned a higher number than the river or stream into which they discharge. For example, all immediate tributaries of the main stream are assigned the number “2.” Tributaries that discharge into a “2” are assigned the number “3,” and so on.

In the QGIS environment, starting from the Orco River layer, vertices were extracted from the linear geometry using the “Extract vertices” function. The elevations were extracted by giving the extracted vertices and the 5-m resolution raster of the catchment area as input to the “Sample raster values” function.

The hydrodynamic curve for the Orco River basin (Figure 65) is visualized in the Python environment, and the areas of interest are calculated by numerical integration.

Figure 64 Orco river hierarchical structure

Figure 65 Orco river hydrodynamic curve

Objective 2 – Task3

Some of the outputs from the above-described framework are reported in the present section. The simulation period is from 2014 to 2021 .

The results refer to a spatial modeling of the basin up to Ceresole Dam.

For clarity, the resulting graphs reported represents one-year (2017) simulation under three different **simplified scenarios** (see Table 3). Each scenario simulates distinct turbine operation strategies applied within the modeled basin. For each of the three scenarios, two

subplots are given. The first shows the average daily input flow rates, output flow rate for hydropower purposes, ecological runoff, and spilled flow rate. In the second subplot, the annual storage trend is reported. Varying boundary conditions influence the reservoir storage dynamics, resulting in differences in energy production and water release patterns throughout the year.

Table 3 Scenarios definition

Name	Turbine operating hours	Temperature-constraint	Maximum Output [m³/s]
Time restricted turbine operation	Declared by IREN	No	7
Unconstrained turbine operation	No	No	7
Temperature dependent turbine operation	No	No operations below 3 degrees	7

Figure 66 Output results of three different scenarios (Table 3). First subplot: daily input and output flow rates. Second subplot: Annual storage behavior

Deviations (if applicable):

As mentioned in RM2 , Objective 1-Task3 and Objective 2-Task1 of RM2 have been moved in RM4 activities, in particular in the Objective2 – task3 “Implementation of an Integrated Watershed model of the Orco valley”.

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

15 Davis weather stations have been purchased and will be installed in the Orco Valley.

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

Objective2 – Task3

As we move forward, our focus will be on advancing the integrated management of water and energy resources of the Orco Valley through the following strategic scenarios (Screening of the possible actions section).

First, we will explore scenarios involving the **energy market**, which will directly influence how hydropower production is managed. These **non-structural, management actions**

require ongoing decision-making based on external factors, such as energy market fluctuations and demand. By aligning hydropower production with market trends, we can observe how the water resource will be affected by maximizing the energy output. Next, we will consider scenarios that involve the **construction of new dams**, assessing the hydrodynamic curve already developed. These represent **structural, planning actions**—once completed, they remain in place for the long term. Unlike management decisions, which must be revisited periodically, these infrastructure projects are foundational and create lasting changes in the system's capacity and resilience. Lastly, we will continue to expand our efforts with **the modeling of other system components** to further refine and enhance our understanding of the entire basin system (Modeling of the Watershed section).

Key Indicators for Research activities and Flagship Projects, cumulative since the beginning of the Flagship Project:

Research Booster	KPI description	Description	KPI Target	KPI Actual
Outcome	3.1.1 Number of Pilot Line / Demonstrators / Prototypes		1	0
	3.1.2.a Number of publications	This includes all publications with DOI indexing (or equivalent), specifically but not limited to: - Articles in scientific journals, provided they undergo peer review (excluding 'predatory' journals) - Review papers - Doctoral theses - Monographs - Proceeding papers, if peer-reviewed - Conference proceedings, provided they are peer-reviewed	29	28
	3.1.2.b Number of FP deliverables	Number of deliverables and working papers, as declared in the Flagship Projects. The deliverables should be uploaded on ZENODO.	13	9
	3.1.3 Number of registered IPR (patents, utility models, trademarks, industrial designs)	Number of new patents filed since the start of Nodes, in Spoke topics, by critical mass researchers (patent topic must be linked to NODES - flagships projects or PoC).	1	0 ¹
Output	3.1.5 Number of professor and researcher involved	CRITICAL MASS involved in the Spoke (only STRUCTURED personnel). The indicator is updated only if there are changes in the Critical Mass	14	37
	3.1.6 Personnel effort dedicated to Research and Innovation and Flagship Project	Man-months for the period related to CRITICAL MASS. This is a cumulative indicator: the goal is to approach the target by the end of the project	130	85 ²

¹ See annex (I) for more detail

² Data as 30 September 2024

2 IMPACT

According to the EUSALP strategy, digitalization through connectivity and digital services can be a way to address the critical challenges of mountain areas, such as depopulation, brain drain, physical barriers, accessibility to welfare and economic growth (www.alpine-region.eu). Based on this line of reasoning, this flagship project considers the use of digital technologies to improve the performance of enterprises located in mountain areas by reducing or resolving the critical issues identified in the EUSALP strategy. In addition, digital technologies can be a way to combat the brain drain by attracting and retaining skilled workers in mountain regions. Digitalization becomes important to an efficient and sustainable use of water and energy resources, to reduce travel and to make it easier living in mountain areas for people working for companies wherever located on the territory of the ecosystem (mountain and plain).

To date, the project's progress has focused on the area of academic research and has generated a good number of scientific publications with a significant impact in the scientific field. Also, some monitoring innovative sensors have been tested at different altitudes, sometime helped by mountain industry (e.g.: Monterosa2000). In the coming period, an increased impact can be expected in other fields such as industrial production (start of activities of the companies selected in the cascading calls).

3 INDUSTRY PARTICIPATION AND INNOVATIONS (prototypes, clinical trials, Testing activities etc)

The flagship project will generate significant industrial impact in the NODES ecosystem through the digital transformation of some key activities in mountain areas. Digital transformation is brought forward through different transmission channels. By providing innovative digital solutions for firms in the realm of smart working and digital compliance, it contributes to digital transformation of the economic fabric of the territory. New organizational forms leading to inflows of high-skilled workers from different part of the NODES ecosystem to the mountain areas generate the knowledge spillovers and new start-up. Demand for new services from delocalized working activities as well as the definition of new digital solutions for firms and citizens stimulates the creation of new innovative and digitally oriented firms. In the context of green development, innovation activities can not only promote the efficiency of resource allocation and enhance the core competitiveness but can also drive the high-quality socio-economic development of the region. During the reporting period, discussions continued with the main companies and stakeholders in the NODES area. The project promoted with companies the opportunities related to the cascading calls published by the NODES project. Activities are at a preliminary stage, the companies involved in the cascading calls just started their activities.

A meeting between the coordinator of module 1 and Hortus was done at the Hortus headquarters in Gallarate the 24th Oct. in order to discuss in presence with the German producer of GNSS antennas for snow water equivalent measurement to be installed in three sites.

Collaboration with a number of companies focused on environmental monitoring took place such as with Finapp Srl, ANavS GmbH, Hortus Srl, JB Hyperspectral Devices GmbH, and LEN Srl. Furthermore, to booster the research potential, collaborations with different institutes of the National Research Council of Italy has been implemented such as with IRSA (Water Research Institute), ISP (Institute of Polar Sciences), and IIA (Institute of Atmospheric pollution Research).

4 FOLLOW-UP OF RECOMMENDATIONS AND COMMENTS FROM PREVIOUS REVIEW(S) (IF APPLICABLE)

Comments received in internal reviews have been incorporated and implemented.

5 OPEN SCIENCE PRACTISES AND UPDATE OF THE DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (IF APPLICABLE)

Project deliverables and new datasets uploaded on ZENODO platform following the principle of Open FAIR Data .

6 RESULTS BEYOND THE STATE OF THE ART

The following Table offers preliminary list of potential beneficiaries and target groups for each of the 4 RM's.

RM	Title	Topics	Potential beneficiaries / Target groups
1	<i>Monitoring and forecasting water resources and energy productivity at the watershed scale</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Innovative sensors and procedures</i> • <i>Monitoring</i> • <i>Data Analysis and Forecasting</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Local Agencies & Research Centers (data collection, analysis and innovative sensors)</i> • <i>Civil Protection (early warnings and forecasting)</i>
2	<i>Integrated management of energy production and use</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Development of a co-simulation platform for management of energy and water resources in REC</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>REC administrators (Design of new REC, Simulation of different Scenarios and Performance Analysis)</i>

3	<i>Risk-resilient Energy and Water Infrastructures</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Avalanches</i> • <i>Slope Stability</i> • <i>Earth Dams stability</i> • <i>Landslides</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Local Agencies (Risk analysis, guidelines, eg...)</i> • <i>Civil Protection (early warnings, management plans)</i>
4	<i>Smart Energy and Water Distribution Systems</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Digital Models</i> • <i>Water & energy production/management</i> • <i>Integrated watershed models</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Local Agencies (Resources availability, almost Real-time data visualization)</i> • <i>Energy production companies (water resource & water demand prediction for better management)</i> • <i>REC (resources available, integration with co-simulation platform described in RM2)</i>

ANNEXES

A) LIST OF ALL DELIVERABLES.

D. No	Name	RM No	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)	Status	Comments	DOI
D1	Flagship Work Programme	/		R	PU	M2		30/11/2022	Submitted		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11093732
D2	Technical Call fiche	/		OTHER	PU	M2		30/11/2022	Accepted	Calls published by M2, Hiring completed	
D3	Geodatabase structure	All		OTHER	SEN	M12		31/10/2023	Submitted		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11093802
D4	Progress Report Flagship Projects SUMMER	All		R	PU	M12		31/10/2023	Submitted		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11124821
D5	First dataset delivery	All		DATA	PU	M12		31/10/2023	Submitted		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11093819
D6	Digital Twin (beta version)	All		DEM	SEN	M18		31/04/2024	Submitted		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11094156
D7	Innovative Sensors (first release)	RM1		DEM	SEN	M18		31/03/2024	Submitted		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11124737
D8	Second progress report	all		R	PU	M24		31/10/2024	Submitted	This document	
D9	Second dataset delivery	all		DATA	SEN	M24		31/10/2024	Submitted		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14016541
D10	Geological survey	RM3	UNIBAS	DATA	SEN	M25			Pending		

D11	Model of a hydrological response	RM1	UNIBAS	OTHER	PU	M30			Pending		
D12	Final report	all		R	SEN	M36			Pending		
D13	Final dataset delivery	all		DATA	PU	M36			Pending		
D14	Digital twin (final version)	all		DEM	SEN	M36			Pending		
D15	Innovative sensors (final release)	all		DEM	SEN	M36			Pending		

Table 4: Deliverables

B) LIST OF MILESTONES

Milestone No	Milestone Name	RM No	Lead Beneficiary	Means of Verification	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)	Achieved	Comments
1	Launch of research	all		Deliverables D1-D2	M6		M6	YES	
2	First Dataset Delivery	all		Deliverables D3-D4-D5	M12		M12	YES	
3	Digital Twin & Innovative Sensor – First Releases	all		Deliverables D6-D7	M18		M18	YES	
4	Second Dataset Delivery	all		Deliverables D8 -D9	M24		M24	YES	
5	Digital Twin & Innovative Sensor – Final Releases	all		Deliverables D10 – D11 –D12 – D13 – D14 - D15	M36				

Table 5: Milestones

C) LIST OF CRITICAL RISKS

State of play: Give the state of play of the risks that were identified (and new risks that materialised during project implementation) and add new mitigation measures, if needed.

Risk No	Did you apply risk mitigation measures?	Did your risk materialize?	Comments
1	NO	NO	No partner-related risk issues have been identified so far
2	NO	NO	No planning problem have been indentified so far.
3	NO	NO	Research activities have not produced any critical issues concerning changes of priorities in research projects so far.
4	NO	NO	The solutions developed are undergoing, but so far no problems with scalability or lower than expected results have been reported.
5	YES	Partially	Data availability is crucial. To mitigate this risk, appropriate data harvesting mechanisms are set in place to track progress of availability of data.
6	NO	NO	The solutions developed and the results during the period have been published in scientific journals and presented at conferences.

Table 6: Risks

D) PROJECT PATHWAY TO IMPACT: RESULTS

As described in the previous chapters, research activities have begun to produce some significant initial results summarized in the table below.

Name	Result type	TRLs	Steps undertaken towards exploitation (multiple choice)	Market maturity (state of the market targeted by this result)
Guidelines for the geophysical characterization of rockfall protection embankments	METH	6		
Innovative procedure for assessing the water balance of a mountain basin with a significant snow contribution	METH	7	[Prototyping in laboratory environment] [Intellectual property management]	
Co-simulation platform for management of energy and water resources in REC	SCI	3		
Digital platform for geospatial data visualization	PROD	5		
Implementation of an Integrated Watershed model of the Orco valley.	SCI	2		

Table 7: Results

E) PUBLICATIONS

Type of publication	Peer - review	Type of PID	PID of deposited publication	Link to publication	Title of the publication	PID of publisher version of record	ISSN/ eSSN	Authors	Title of the journal or equivalent	Number	Publisher	Month/ Year of publication	PID of book	Book title	Was the publication available in open access through the repository at the time of publication	License type
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.159195		A stochastic cellular automaton model to describe the evolution of the snow-covered area across a high-elevation mountain catchment			K.J. Painter, A. Gentile, S. Ferraris	Science of The Total Environment	857	ELSEVIER	ott-22			YES	CC BY
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.3390/geosciences13050147		Towards a Hybrid Design Approach of Anchored Drapery Systems			M. Marchelli, A. Pol, D. Peila, F. Gabrieli	Geosciences 2023	13(5)	MDPI	mar-23			YES	CC BY
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.162777		Hydrological, thermal and chemical influence of an intact rock glacier discharge on mountain stream water			F. Bearzot, et al.	Science of The Total Environment	876	ELSEVIER	mar-23			NO	Other

Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2022-921		Towards a conceptualization of the hydrological processes behind changes of young water fraction with elevation: a focus on mountainous alpine catchments			A. Gentile, D. Canone, N. Ceperley, D. Gisolo, M. Previati, G. Zuecco, B. Schaeffli, S. Ferraris	Hydrology and Earth System Sciences	27	EGU	mag-23			YES	CC BY
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3275435		A Comparative Evaluation of Deep Learning Techniques for Photovoltaic Panel Detection From Aerial Images			E. Arnaudo, G. Blanco, F. Dominici	IEEE Access	11	IEEE	mag-23			YES	CC BY
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.segan.2023.101072		A Multi-Agent Framework for Smart Grid Simulations: Strategies for power-to-heat flexibility management in residential context.			Rando Mazzarino P., Macii A., Bottaccioli L., Patti E.,	Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks, Elsevier	34	ELSEVIER	mag-23			YES	CC BY
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/acdb88		Unprecedented snow-drought conditions in the Italian Alps during the early 2020s			N. Colombo et al.	Environmental research letters	18	IOPscience	giu-23			YES	CC BY
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijrmms.2023.105551		Rockfall in open pit mines: management of the pit geometry and protection measures design			M. Marchelli, D. Peila, A. Giacomini	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ROCK MECHANICS AND MINING SCIENCES	170	Elsevier	lug-23			YES	CC BY

Publication in conference proceeding	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1109/IGARSS52108.2023.10281933		LAND COVER SEGMENTATION WITH SPARSE ANNOTATIONS FROM SENTINEL-2 IMAGERY			M. Galatola, E. Arnaudo, L. Barco, C. Rossi, F. Dominici	Proceedings of the IEEE International Symposium on Geoscience and Remote Sensing		IEEE	lug-23			YES	CC BY
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2023.1234976		Editorial: Hydrological and chemical effects of a changing cryosphere on mountain freshwaters			Nicola Colombo, et al	Frontiers in Earth Sciences	11	Frontiers	lug-23			YES	CC BY
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2023.106307		Towards a procedure to manage safety on construction sites of rockfall protective measures			M. Marchelli, G. Coltrinari, G.A. Degan, D. Peila	Safety Science	168	Elsevier	set-23			YES	CC BY
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2023.121749		An Online Reinforcement Learning Approach for HVAC Control.			Solinas F.M, Macii A., Patti E., Bottaccioli L.,	Expert Systems with Applications	238	ELSEVIER	set-23			YES	CC BY NC ND
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2023-1797		Technical Note: two-component Electrical Conductivity-based hydrograph separation employing an EXPonential mixing model (EXPECT) provides reliable high temporal resolution young water fraction estimates in three small Swiss catchments			A. Gentile, J. von Freyberg, D. Gisolo, D. Canone, S. Ferraris	Hydrology and Earth System Sciences	28	EGU	set-23			YES	CC BY

Publication in conference proceeding	YES	pURL	https://arc.lib.montana.edu/snow-science/item.php?id=2910		A MULTILEVEL FRAMEWORK FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF ENERGY INFRASTRUCTURES INVOLVED BY AVALANCHES			E. Bovet, V. De Biagi, N. Durand, A. Debernardi, M. Marchelli, S. Roveyaz	International Snow Science Workshop Proceedings 2023, Bend, Oregon		ISSW	ott-23			YES	CC BY
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-023-01331-y		Local cooling and drying induced by Himalayan glaciers under global warming			Franco Salerno, et al.	Nature Geoscience	16	Nature Publishing Group	dic-23			YES	CC BY
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1007/s12273-024-1109-6		An innovative heterogeneous transfer learning framework to enhance the scalability of deep reinforcement learning controllers in buildings with integrated energy systems			Coraci D., Brandi S., Hong T., Capozzoli A.	Building Simulation	17	Springer	feb-24			YES	CC BY
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2023.107635		High-resolution temporal variations of nitrate in a high-elevation pond in alpine tundra (NW Italian Alps)			N. Colombo, et al.	Catena	235	ELSEVIER	feb-24			NO	CC BY
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.5194/ascmo-10-51-2024		Applying different methods to model dry and wet spells at daily scale in a large range of rainfall regimes across Europe			Baiamonte G., Agnese C., Cammalleri C., Di Nardo E., Ferraris S., Martini T.	Advances in Statistical Climatology, Meteorology and Oceanography	10	Copernicus Publications	mar-24			YES	CC BY

Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2024.131223		Evapotranspiration of an abandoned grassland in the Italian Alps: Modeling the impact of shrub encroachment			Davide Gisolo, et al.	Journal of Hydrology	635	ELSEVIER	apr-24			YES	CC BY
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2024.123447		Real building implementation of a deep reinforcement learning controller to enhance energy efficiency and indoor temperature control			Alberto Silvestri, et al.	Applied Energy	368	ELSEVIER	ago-24			YES	CC BY
Publication in conference proceeding	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2405.20109		FMARS: Annotating Remote Sensing Images for Disaster Management using Foundation Models			Arnaudo, E., Vaschetti, J. L., Innocenti, L., Barco, L., Lisi, D., Fissore, V., & Rossi, C.	Proceedings of the IEEE International Symposium on Geoscience and Remote Sensing		IEEE	lug-24			YES	CC BY
Publication in conference proceeding	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2405.20161		Landslide mapping from Sentinel-2 imagery through change detection			Monopoli, T., Montello, F., & Rossi, C.	Proceedings of the IEEE International Symposium on Geoscience and Remote Sensing		IEEE	lug-24			YES	CC BY
Publication in conference proceeding	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2405.20731	-	Maximum Temperature Prediction Using Remote Sensing Data via Convolutional Neural Network			Innocenti L., Blanco G., Barco L., Rossi C.	IEEE MetroLivEnv		IEEE	giu-24			YES	CC BY
Publication in conference proceeding	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2408.16792		Uncertainty-aware segmentation for rainfall prediction post processing			Monaco S., Monaco L., Apiletti D.	2024 ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining Workshops		ACM	set-24			YES	CC BY

Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.8643		Analysis of diurnal air temperature trends and pattern similarities in Highland and Lowland stations of Italy and UK			Liyew, C., Ferraris S., et al.	International J. of Climatology, Royal Soc. of Met.		Wiley	ott-24			YES	CC BY
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2024.121381		Using stable isotopes to inform water resource management in forested and agricultural ecosystems			Scandellari, Ferraris S., et al.	J. Environmental Management	365	ELSEVIER	giu-24			YES	CC BY
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2409.17732		Identifying Time Patterns of Highland and Lowland Air Temperature Trends in Italy and UK across monthly and annual scales			Liyew, C., Ferraris S., et al.	Advances in Statistical Climatology, Meteorology and Oceanography		Copernicus Publications	set-24			YES	CC BY
Article in journal	YES	DOI	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.175706		Factors controlling the water quality of rock glacier springs in European and American mountain ranges alpine tundra (NW Italian Alps)			S.Brighenti, N. Colombo, et al.	Science of The Total Environment	953	ELSEVIER	ago-24			YES	CC BY

Table 8: Publications

F) DATASETS

Integrated Dataset of the Four Research Module.

The updated integrated dataset of the four research modules was delivered. The dataset represents the general repository structure and contains an initial collection of data of the four RMs. The repository will continue to be populated throughout the duration of the project in order to ensure that the desired results are achieved in terms of the Digital Twin platform.

Short Name:	FS-SUMMER
Description of datasets:	Integrated dataset of the 4 RMs
Data origin:	31/10/2023
Data type:	Numeric, geospatial, time-dependant
Data Formats:	Multiple: .csv, .shp, .gtif, .xlsx, .pdf
Useful for whom:	Digital Twin platform
If data is needed to validate conclusions of a scientific publication, describe the provisions whereby you intend to make it available	[N/A]
Findability (Type of PID, PID of deposited dataset):	https://github.com/FS-SUMMER/Dataset.git
Accessibility:	<i>Partially open, access with request</i>
Interoperability:	
Reusability:	GNU General Public License v3.0 GNU General Public License v3.0
Open	YES

Table 9: Data sets

Flow Duration Curves (FDC) & Hydropower Potential

Preliminary dataset containing the outputs of Task 1.1-Objective2 and Task 2.1-Objective 2 of Research Module 4.

Short Name:	SUMMER - Flow Duration Curves & Hydropower Potential - RM4
Description of datasets:	Dataset containing the results of the flow duration curves (FDC) and the hydroelectric potential along the entire Orco Valley hydrographic network
Data origin:	30/04/2024
Data type:	Numeric, geospatial
Data Formats:	Multiple: .csv, .shp,
Useful for whom:	
If data is needed to validate conclusions of a scientific publication, describe the provisions whereby you intend to make it available	[N/A]
Findability (Type of PID, PID of deposited dataset):	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11093874
Accessibility:	Open
Interoperability:	
Reusability:	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
Open	YES

Table 10: Data sets

Orco Valley Geopackage

A Geopackage containing all the geodata necessary to the implementation of an Integrated Watershed model of the Orco valley.

Short Name:	SUMMER - OrcoValley_Geopackage - RM4
Description of datasets:	A Geopackage containing all the geodata necessary to the implementation of an Integrated Watershed model of the Orco Valley
Data origin:	30/04/2024
Data type:	Numeric, geospatial, time dependant
Data Formats:	.gpkg
Useful for whom:	Integrated Watershed model application (RM4)
If data is needed to validate conclusions of a scientific publication, describe the provisions whereby you intend to make it available	[N/A]
Findability (Type of PID, PID of deposited dataset):	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11093889
Accessibility:	Open
Interoperability:	
Reusability:	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
Open	YES

Table 11: Data sets

Water Balance – Innovative Procedure

A dataset containing all the data collected according to the innovative procedure described in Deliverable SUMMER-D7_Innovative Sensor (first Release).

Short Name:	SUMMER – Water_balance – RM1
Description of datasets:	A dataset containing water balance data from Research Module 1, collected according to the innovative procedure described in Deliverable SUMMER-D7_Innovative Sensor (first Release).
Data origin:	30/04/2024
Data type:	Numeric, geospatial, time dependant
Data Formats:	.csv
Useful for whom:	Innovative Sensors (RM1)
If data is needed to validate conclusions of a scientific publication, describe the provisions whereby you intend to make it available	<i>The dataset will be made public following the publication of a scientific article on the innovative procedure it refers to.</i>
Findability (Type of PID, PID of deposited dataset):	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11122068
Accessibility:	<i>Restricted</i>
Interoperability:	
Reusability:	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
Open	<i>NO</i>

Table 12: Data sets

Co-Simulation Platform – Example of use

A dataset containing the data and outputs of the co-simulation platform used for an initial example of use in the case study of the municipality of Frassinetto.

Short Name:	SUMMER - Co-Simulation Platform_Oct24 - RM2
Description of datasets:	A dataset containing the data and outputs of the co-simulation platform developed by Research Module 2, used for an initial example of use in the case study of the municipality of Frassinetto.
Data origin:	31/10/2024
Data type:	Numeric, geospatial, time dependant
Data Formats:	.zip
Useful for whom:	REC / Co-Simulation Platform users (RM2)
If data is needed to validate conclusions of a scientific publication, describe the provisions whereby you intend to make it available	
Findability (Type of PID, PID of deposited dataset):	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14012238
Accessibility:	Open
Interoperability:	
Reusability:	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
Open	YES

Table 13: Data sets

I) INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS (IPRs)

Research activities within RM1 led to the filing of a patent related to the development of an innovative methodology for monitoring small mountain basins. The patent application was accepted without reservation on 25 Oct 2024.

Type of IP Rights	Application Title	Application Reference	Application Date	IPR Owner	IPR Status Has protection been awarded?	IPR Award Reference ID
[Patent] [Trademark] [Registered design] [Utility model] [Other]	[insert title of the application]	[OPTION for international applications of patents [insert IP international organisation code] [insert serial number]] [OPTION for national applications of patents [insert country code (two letters)] [insert serial number]] [OPTION for other registered IPR: [insert application reference country code (two letters) or organisation code]] [insert alpha numeric identifier]] [insert EPO/google patent format] [insert application ID]	[dd/mm/yyyy]	[insert owner name(s)]	[YES] [NO] [N/A]	[insert reference]

Table 14: IPRs

J) OTHER RESULTS

Given its nature and starting from a low TRL, the project required time to achieve initial results. In the coming year, many additional products will be developed.

Type of result	Description	If the result is needed to validate the conclusions of a publication, describe the provisions whereby you intend to make your output available, either in digital or physical form	TRLs	Type of PID (if available)	PID (if available)	URL to repository landing page for the result service/webpage hosting the result (if available)	What license is the result under
[Software] [Workflow] [Protocol] [Prototype] [Other]	[insert description]	[N/A] [open access given to data] [[other: please describe]]	Expected by Project 'end: [TRL1: Basic principles observed] [TRL2: Technology concept validated] [TRL3: Experimental proof of concept] [TRL4: Technology validated in lab] [TRL5: Technology validated in relevant environment] [TRL6: Technology demonstrated in relevant environment] [TRL7: System prototype demonstration in operational environment] [TRL8: System complete and qualified] [TRL9: Actual system proven in operational environment] [Not applicable]	[DOI] [handle] [ARK] [URI] [Other]	[insert PID reference]	[insert URL]	[CCBY or equivalent] [CC0 or equivalent to CC0] [Other]

Table 15: Other results

K) IMPACT in terms of TRLs, SDGs, KSOs

Technology readiness level of the project	
At project' start: TRL1 Current status: TRL4	Expected by Project 'end: [TRL6 - Technology demonstrated in relevant environment] or [TRL7 - System prototype demonstration in operational environment]

Table 16: TRLs

Is your project likely to deliver results relevant for the following Sustainable Development Goals?	
Climate neutrality (SDG 13)	[Fully relevant]
Clean Water and Sanitation (SDG 6)	[Fully relevant]
Life Below Water (SDG 14)	[Not relevant]
Life on Land (SDG 15)	[Partially relevant]
No Poverty	[Partially relevant]
Zero Hunger	[Not relevant]
Good Health and Well-being	[Not relevant]
Gender Equality	[Not relevant]
Decent Work and Economic Growth (SDG 8)	[Partially relevant]
Affordable and Clean Energy (SDG 7)	[Fully relevant]
Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure (SDG 9)	[Fully relevant]
Reduced Inequality	[Partially relevant]
Sustainable Cities and Communities (SDG 11)	[Fully relevant]
Responsible Consumption and Production (SDG 12)	[Partially relevant]

Quality Education	[Not relevant]
Peace and Justice Strong Institutions	[Not relevant]
International cooperation	[Not relevant]
Please explain your choice	<p>The SUMMER flagship project aims to accompany energy and water management into the digital era, showing how smart technology can boost the integrated management of water and energy systems (SDG 6) fostering the sustainable production and distribution of energy (SDG7). Digital technologies, combined with the power of 'big data' and AI-based analytics, drive unprecedented innovation in how energy and water utilities and companies manage these vital resources (SDG 8 / SDG 9), contributing to protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems (SDG15) and combatting climate change (SDG 13).</p> <p>Working with local stakeholders and raising awareness among policymakers and industry in the tangible benefits for a transition towards a Circular Economy helps NODES' cities and communities to implement integrated policies and plans towards resource efficiency, mitigation and adaptation to climate change (SDG 11).</p>

Table 17: SDGs

Horizon Europe KEY STRATEGIC ORIENTATIONS (KSO)	Horizon Europe Impact Areas	Contribution to the KSO and the relevant expected impacts
KSO 1 Promoting an open strategic autonomy by leading the development of key digital and enabling technologies, sectors and value chains to accelerate and steer the digital and green transitions through human-centred technologies and innovations	A competitive and secure data-economy	
	Industrial leadership in key and emerging technologies that work for people	
	Secure and cyber secure digital technology	
	High quality digital services for all	The realisation of a digital twin platform on a basin scale to enable optimised management of energy and water resources.
KSO 2 Restoring Europe's ecosystems and biodiversity, and managing sustainably natural resources to ensure food security and a clean and healthy environment	Enhancing ecosystems and biodiversity on land and in waters	
	Clean and healthy air, water and soil	
	Sustainable food systems and nutrition security	
KSO 3 Making Europe the first digitally led circular, climate-neutral and sustainable economy through the transformation of its mobility, energy, construction and production systems	Climate change mitigation and adaptation	This project fosters climate resilience promoting an optimization of energy consumptions at the local scale, promoting renewable energy, and enhancing ecosystem restoration. It empowers communities to adapt sustainably and creating lasting environmental and economic benefits.
	Affordable and clean energy	The implementation of a co-simulation platform for optimizing the production and energy needs of mountain energy communities, together with the development of integrated models for water resource management
	Smart and sustainable transport	
	Circular and clean economy	This project fosters the optimization of resources, creating sustainable value, contributing to a greener and more responsible future.
KSO 4 Creating a more resilient, inclusive and democratic European society, prepared and responsive to threats and disasters, addressing inequalities and providing high-quality health	A resilient EU prepared for emerging threats	The development of models, fragility curves, and guidelines to reduce climate change risks-associated by fostering more resilient communities.

Table 18: KSOs and Impact Areas - HE